

Deciphering the Neolithic Symbolic Language: the Exogamic Key

Cédric Bodet

Abstract: The layout composing the elements of the Anatolian Neolithic symbolism (bull horns, parturient females, migrating birds, zigzagging snakes, teeth-baring animals, cross-like geometric signs and others) is remarkably systematic. Such regularity indicates that the compositions are planned in advance as if meant to convey a predefined message. Making these observations about 30 years ago, the late professor J.D. Forest (Sorbonne University) dug up concepts once much discussed in social anthropology, such as ‘exogamy’ and ‘dualism’ to apply them to the rich iconography of the site of Çatalhöyük. He obtained surprising results, though largely overlooked, as he was literally able to decipher the bulk of the message encoded therein. In the meantime, excavations at Göbekli Tepe and several other contemporary sites (Nevalı Çori, Körtik Tepe, Sayburç, etc.) uncovered an outstanding series of Neolithic pictorial compositions, mainly featuring the same signs and isomorphic arrangement (*i.e.*, one side generally reflecting the other). In the past few years, the present author has applied Forest’s method to many of these pictures with the same coherent results, confirming that, far from being random, these images are all related to the same exogamic scheme.

Neolithic symbolic imagery thus appears as an archaic ‘ideogram script’ arranged according to a ‘syntax’, with each of the 75 pictures analysed here emphasising a slightly different aspect of the same general message. The latter seemingly states that the community’s perpetual cycle of life and death is fundamentally dependent on the respect of the exogamic principle (which the advent of agriculture was, in the Neolithic, directly threatening). Such concepts naturally find their way into highly symbolic places since they devise an essential rule for these communities, namely the reciprocal exchange of partners. In other words, places like Göbekli Tepe and Çatalhöyük are here argued to be an ‘open book’ for the ‘initiated’ viewer of the Neolithic Symbolic Language (NSL).

Keywords: symbolic language (or symbolism), exogamy, Neolithic society, Göbekli Tepe, Çatalhöyük

Introduction

Some thirty years ago, the late Jean-Daniel Forest (1993) endeavoured to decipher the bulk of the message contained in the rich symbolism of Neolithic Çatalhöyük, Central Anatolia. He did it mainly by combining two factors: first, he had observed that in many decorated houses, the same symbolic elements were systematically arranged in a similar relation to each other, implying a predefined pattern or template; in its epistemological sense, a ‘symbol’ indeed contains a “necessary relation between complementary elements” (Augé 1994: 88). Second, Forest’s vast ethnographic knowledge of pre-state societies, notably their kinship patterns and ideology, helped him to provide meaning to these recurrent patterns and, in particular, to the isomorphic arrangement pertaining to most wall paintings, moulded reliefs and figurines found at the site. He thus connected these dualistic compositions to one specific idea, exogamy, which is an early form of prohibition of incest, a fundamental principle of social life among traditional communities, nothing less than the rule distinguishing humanity

from the rest of the animal world, according to Lévi-Strauss (1967). Forest later added a few insights that strengthened his findings and methodology (Forest 1994, 2003, 2006, 2009).

The present author subsequently applied the same methodology to explore the symbolism of Göbekli Tepe and a few other early Neolithic sites like Nevalı Çori or Körtik Tepe (Bodet 2012, 2021, 2023). The results essentially confirmed Forest’s (1993: 37-42, 2006: 133-136) intuition that, with minor local adjustments, an akin symbolic system infused the symbolism of the entire Neolithic period in Southwest Asia, with probable roots in the Palaeolithic (as Mellaart [1967: 24] had already suggested), as well as a lasting influence on the following ages.

After discussing the exogamic principle, the logic and ‘grammar’ structuring the prehistoric pictograms in a coherent semantic system (Anati 2003: 347-359) will be presented, followed by a ‘sign-list’ (or ideogram-list) standing for the basic ‘concepts’ enclosed in the Neolithic Symbolic Language (NSL). Subsequently, more than seventy figurative compositions, single images and geometric signs are analysed and

‘translated’ to confirm Jak Yakar’s impression (2016: 165) that “most signs and abstract motifs in prehistoric art inventories were meant to express (...) culturally inherited spiritual notions in a developed (...) language of symbols (of) metaphoric and communicative values”.

Some Methodology: on the Symbolic Code

With a few exceptions (Matthews 2003: 37; Voigt 2002: 254; Guilaine 2003: 40), Forest’s findings have remained mostly overlooked, notably because concepts like kinship patterns and exogamy, which don’t leave discernible traces on the material remains, rarely find their way into archaeological problematics. Another prerequisite of this methodology is the idea that the represented images ought never to be ‘read’ at their face value but for the concepts they embody (Forest 2009: 113-4), entirely in the way letters, signs and words are used in any particular writing system, making sense only to whoever is literate in them.

Thus, Neolithic images should be apprehended as “some kind of pictogram” (Forest 1994: 122) or, better still, as ‘ideograms’ since they stand for concepts more than material objects *per se*. Clare Gibson’s (2009) book title, ‘How to Read Symbols’ is a good illustration of this approach. Also, the idea that these depictions may represent a notion or a message is often dismissed in favour of our modern concept of ‘art’; that is, they are usually considered as esthetic expressions or as depictions of narrative scenes (Özdoğan E. 2022: 1604). Both views are hardly antithetical. For example, Lorblanchet (2017: 47) convincingly argues that beauty ensures the efficiency of the magic or power contained in the images of the Upper Palaeolithic Franco-Cantabrian cave paintings. As for the Neolithic depictions discussed herewith, it isn’t easy to talk of extreme aesthetic beauty. Yet, they convey and enforce the ‘magical’ occurrence in real life of specifically intended concepts, quite like modern believers do in the presence of religious symbols. Ethnographers and sociologists like Bourdieu (1980) have long claimed that early societies lived in symbolic worlds where nothing is random and *social concepts* are conspicuously displayed. “There is a logic to the symbol (...), coherent, logically connected with one another (...) systemically formulated, translated into rational terms.” (Eliade 1991: 37 [1952: 9]).

The content of the message remains to be unveiled, and this is where the ethnography of extant kinship systems will prove indispensable: ideologies can only be apprehended from the study of living societies. Mithen (1996: 180) indicates a promising direction to look at: “The complex and multiple meanings that may be found in the simplest geometric designs found in Palaeolithic art can be illustrated with (...) the art of the Australian Aborigines. (...) Their

paintings have a basic geometric template underlying the design.” What is interesting here is the “basic geometric template” structuring the apparent variety. The Aborigines analogy, as attempted by Testart (1978, 1985: 432-465), indeed shows that the general matter behind their symbolism and mythology systematically relates to the social organisation ensuring the production and reproduction of the community. So, the first step is to expose the relevant social structures on which these concepts are based.

The Exogamic Social Structure

Gordon Childe’s far-reaching social insight deserves mention here, all the more so that it pre-dates the advent of the structuralist school *per se*: “Undoubtedly the co-operative activities involved in ‘Neolithic’ life found outward expression in social and political institutions. Undoubtedly, such institutions were consolidated and reinforced by magico-religious sanctions, by a more or less *coherent system of beliefs* and superstitions, by what Marxists would call an *ideology*.” (Childe 1951: 82, my italics)

A society is indeed a coherent system organised through the constant adjustment of its main structures, particularly that of production, reproduction and ideology (Durkheim 1937: 89-123; Giddens 1971: 205-223; Bloch 1983: 8-13). The recognition of this organic system of structures is what allows attempting careful analogies between ethnographical and archaeological data (Trigger 1989: 289-293, 303-312). Ethnologists have long remarked that the attention of traditional communities obsessively focused on matters of kinship and marital alliance, and in particular, on the reciprocity in the distribution of sexual mates among the subgroups (moieties, sections, descent groups or lineages) composing the larger community, say, a clan or a tribe (Morgan 1871: 1-9; Radcliffe-Brown 1952: 98-103; Barnard 1978: 69-71). The importance given to ‘reproduction’ and its strong ties with other structures of the society, in particular economy, *i.e.*, the ‘production’, allows us to think that the ideology shaping the kinship system must reflect on the symbolism of that society (Testart 1985: 491-515; Leroi-Gourhan 1964: 1-9).

Frazer (1910: xii-xiii) synthesises the ‘classificatory’ system first set up by L.H. Morgan (1871), considered to be applicable for “a large part of the human race”, as such: “a community was bisected in two exogamous and intermarrying groups, and all men and women were classified according to the generation and the group to which they belonged”, thus classifying everybody between “possible or impossible husbands and wives”. The groups in question are matri- or patrilineal, with the social identity unilaterally acquired from, respectively, the mother or the father. Furthermore, most early social

anthropologists like Spencer and Gillen (1899: 55), Malinowski (1932: 24-27) and even Freud (1913 [2010: 255-256]) put forward the fact that the early society's primary concern systematically revolves around the concept of exogamy. This fundamental rule enforces everyone to marry outside one's own social subgroup, that is, necessarily into another of the subgroups composing the larger community (Ghasarian 1996: 152-9; Walker *et al.* 2011: 1-4), the opposite subgroup if the latter is divided into only two 'moieties' or 'halves' (a system called 'restricted' by Lévi-Strauss 1967: 80-97). Indeed, such division into at least two marital subgroups appears universal among pre-state social formations. The firm stance of 20th-century structuralism against 19th-century evolutionism (Testart 1992), recognising the dualist system as a pure kinship structure but depriving it of any evolutionary impact, has since led to the damaging disregard of this basal concept. Consequently, to the author's knowledge, exogamy is hardly even mentioned in the numerous works devoted to throwing light on Prehistoric symbolism (see Schoop's eloquent note [2005: 49] on the difficulty of simply mentioning the "moiety system").

Cosmogonies and mythological narratives explaining the birth of the world and of the community are wide-spread among traditional societies (Le Quellec 2015: 259-260). In these, the mysterious process of life, which catalyses the abstract thoughts and considerations of traditional populations, hunter-gatherers and early agriculturalists alike, is systematically conceived together with its opposition, death (Tresidder 2000: 8-15; 2003: 43). There is more to these cosmologies: through narration, they tend to deliver, more or less explicitly, a moral content by recalling the essential organisation and conduct that the community ought to follow regarding the reciprocal exchange of sexual mates to ensure the perpetuation of the whole.

The crucial point that needs to be underlined here is that early communities, called "elementary" by Lévi-Strauss (1967: 33-48) or "universal" by Barnard (1978: 69-71), are small, closed on themselves and generally exclusively composed of blood relatives (affine included). In such a context, the exogamic principle can only materialise through dividing the community into at least two 'moieties' mutually exchanging sexual mates at every generation (Frazer 1910: vol. 4: 106-115). This essential and prevalent form of social arrangement (probably once universal because it is directly related to the survival of the group) seems to stand as a foundation for the entire economic and ideological organisation of these communities, naturally reflecting on their symbolism, in particular on the mythology (Testart 1978), but also on the architectural and pictorial symbolism, as we will try to show.

Social structures do evolve under demographic pressure, for instance, and a two-partite division may, in time, lead to further subdivisions, generally 4, 8 and even 12, thereby enlarging the circle of non-prohibited unions (Frazer 1910). However, whatever the number of exogamic social subgroups composing the society, the primary two-partite division into complementary subparts will long remain a central and basal concept¹ on the ideological level (hence the 'twin problematic' pervasive in many ancient myths, as pointed out by Girard 1972: 213-248). We will see that the two exogamic moieties eternally interact with the endless cycle of Life and Death (Couderc and Sillander 2012: 28-29). A straightforward way to express symbolically the natural complementarity of the division of society into two exogamous groups is the splitting of humanity into male and female halves. This led Leroi-Gourhan's (1964) sociological observation, which the ethnologist Testart (2012: 254, Note 1) was still considering the best explanatory attempt on the subject, that the Franco-Cantabrian cave paintings were organised around "a purely symbolic classification of (animal) species in two complementary halves, one being male [bison], the other female [horse]" (Cauvin 1997: 100). What is thence symbolised behind this complementary opposition of sexual nature is thus, probably, the division of the society into two exogamous (and complementary) moieties. As shown elsewhere (Bodet 2022), it is the same dualist principle which is likely to be embodied in the vast twin pillars standing right in the centre of the symbolic circles (standing for the society?) of the Göbekli Tepe III enclosures. Such a dualistic arrangement has been identified in many other Neolithic symbolic architectures throughout Southwest Asia (Bodet 2023). Exogamy was, indeed, still a matter of utmost importance among early agricultural tribes (which are of concern here), like the Trobriand islanders, enforcing the "duality in tribal division (...) without which no primitive community could exist" according to Malinowski (1932: 24-25 – italics are mine). He eloquently continues: "A dual organisation may appear clearly in the *division* of a tribe into *two 'moieties' (...), a symmetry of structure* will be found in every savage society as the indispensable basis of *reciprocal obligations*".

The *dualist* division of society into two equal subparts (each composed of men and women) designated by unilineal filiation (either through male or female descent), systematically exchanging mates at every generation, is conceived by extant tribes as a primordial concept, on which the mere existence and perpetuation of the community are entirely dependent. On an ideological level, this concept takes the form of intransigent moral values to be enforced and expressed in the symbolism (cosmogonies, iconography) under the form of 'isomorphic' elements (*i.e.*, made of two

equal halves) interacting to ensure the birth of new generations. This dualist/ exogamic program is especially strongly displayed in those places assumed to possess a ‘magical’ aura, likely to play an active role in the fertility of the universe, the community or the lineage, respectively, on hilltops, like Göbekli Tepe (Schmidt 2007a: 19-20), in communal buildings, like Nemrik, Çayönü or Jerf el Ahmar (Kozłowski 1989; Özdoğan and Özdoğan 1998; Stordeur *et al.* 2001) and elders’ dwellings like Çatalhöyük (Hodder’s [2016] “history houses”). The present text aims to show how this dualist ideology reflects on the pictorial symbolism.

The Symbolic Message

Preliminary note: to facilitate the reading, the redundant use of the conditional or adverbials of probability (maybe, perhaps, possibly, seemingly, *etc.*) is at times evaded; nevertheless, given the subject under investigation here, all the propositions suggested cannot be taken for granted and are open for revision, refinement or refuting in future research.

The Basic Duo of the Neolithic Symbolic Language (NSL)

The investigation must start with the Late Neolithic symbolic repertoire of Çatalhöyük because it is the most explicit; earlier compositions, in particular at Göbekli Tepe, come down to the same basic message, but certain elements, not explicitly represented, are only suggested, so their decipherment can only be clarified in retrospect. The most recurrent duo in the symbolism comprises the parturient female figure and the bull (Mellaart 1967: 82-105). The former has nothing to do with real women, as implied by the fact that it is giving birth to the latter (Forest 1993: 4-6), and by the fact that her head is probably that of a carnivorous animal (see below). It is only because it can give life that a woman’s body has been selected as an ideogram to represent the concept of fertility at large (including the concept of rebirth, *infra*). For example, Mellaart (1967: 115) noted that as a symbol of pregnancy and birth, “the navel was always shown”. Concluding her paragraph on ‘vulva and birth’, while referring to female representations from the Palaeolithic all the way to the statuette of Çatalhöyük, Gimbutas (1989: 107) states clearly: “the portrayal of the Goddess in a birth-giving posture for some 20,000 years demonstrates that this aspect of the Deity was a constant focus of attention”. Moreover, as will become apparent, this beneficent aspect of the fertile concept inevitably implies (strongly suggested if not explicitly represented) its maleficent counterpart, death, generally represented by the teeth of carnivorous animals (an act of destroying flesh by devouring, [which, in

turn, allows the body to regenerate though nutrition]).

The second element of the duo, the bull, has likewise nothing to do with the actual animal *per se*. As devised by Forest (1993: 3), the bull would likely stand for society as a whole. The horns, to which the bull is often reduced, emphasise its physical and sexual strength (Chevalier and Gheerbrant 1982: 289). Thus, the parturient-bull duo can be read as ‘the engendering principle delivering the society’. In the utmost complementary opposition, a symbol of the exogamic principle, society is considered a male entity (bull, horns) expressly *because* the ‘engendering’ principle is feminine. Again, actual sexes are not of concern here; we are in a world of pure symbolic abstraction. The image of the fertile dualism between females and males in nature is not chosen to produce a narrative but as a symbol of fertility. So, which complementary opposition is suggested here by this fundamental male/female fecund dichotomy?

It brings forward the complementarity, just reviewed, of society’s two distinct but parallel subparts (exogamic moieties), systematically exchanging nubile mates at every generation to perpetuate the whole. In other words, there must be a primal division (dualism) of the society for the exchange of mates (exogamy) to produce life and, inevitably, death. On a symbolic level, the society as a whole (arguably represented by circular or rectilinear ‘full’ motifs) is divided into two (probably matrilineal though not necessarily) moieties exchanging their males (often represented by triangles) for the fertile principle (symbolised by the ‘female’ figure) to produce the (male) society (the ‘bull’) (Forest 1993: 3-6).

With these basic notions in hand, it is now possible to relate to the general scheme of meaning that Forest deciphered from the set of symbols in Çatalhöyük. The concepts expressed symbolically in the iconography produce a general message which can briefly be summarised as follows: ‘There is an overarching regenerative principle (feminine figure) that continually gives life (via the vagina) to the community (the bull, male) and takes it back through death (by the bare teeth/ mouth). This eternal cycle is set in motion through the union of individuals coming from equal, parallel, interconnected, but strictly separated social subgroups, whether they are moieties (twin steles/ horns) or lineages (parallel lines/snakes). It follows that society must respect dualism and, consequently, the reciprocal exchange of mates (exogamy) between complementary moieties/ lineages to continue perpetuating relentlessly’.

The Geometric Representation of Exogamy

It seems that most symbolic compositions of the NSL refer in one way or another to this general message. In

figurative compositions, it is rarely displayed in totality. However, simple and recurrent geometric signs (e.g., X, + or H) were used to condense this message.

The Greek cross '+' (Fig. 1) is quite common in Neolithic depictions, from the stone bowls of Early Neolithic Körtek to the wall paintings of Late Neolithic Çatalhöyük and the decoration of Halaf pottery. According to Forest's (1993: 12-5) reconstruction, which appears most befitting here, the regenerative principle (1) is placed at the intersection of two lines: on the horizontal axis (time), the principle 'swallows' ascending (dead) generations from the East (2, right) and engenders new ones to the West (3, left) by continually unifying the two exogamic moieties on the northern (4, up) and southern (5, down) ends of the vertical axis (space). If this display is opposite to the course of the sun, it may possibly be because the principle 'makes time' and is not 'produced' by it: ascending generations must first be destroyed before the descending ones are produced.

Fig 1 The regenerative principle (1) at the centre of a Greek cross linking ascending (2, East) to descending (3, West) generations through the interaction of two exogamic moieties (4 + 5/ North-South).

The 'X' shape (Fig. 2) represents the same principle as a template, according to which the four (triangular) elements of the message (life/ death/ the two moieties) unite in one coherent sign. Painted X signs are common on the walls of Çatalhöyük, but Forest (1993: 10-15) reconstructed its meaning by basing himself on the iconographic plan of Çatalhöyük houses. The four side elements must then be conceived as triangles converging towards the regenerative principle at the centre, which continuously absorbs and/ or ejects them. Partner from moiety A (left/ north) merges with

a partner from moiety B (right/ south) on the horizontal axis (space) so that, on the vertical axis (time), ascending (past) generations (up/ east) become descending (future) generations (below/west). Again, death appears to the east because the regenerating principle must first swallow the ascending generations before it gives birth to the west (Forest 1993); also, the only openings in Çatalhöyük houses are on the roof, the rising/ newborn sun enlightens the western wall, whilst the setting/ dying sun enlightens the eastern wall, an expression of Bourdieu's characteristic reversal of the inside and outside of traditional houses (below). The whole figure can indeed be reversed since both moieties are equal and interchangeable and because the descending generations will one day become the ascending ones, the passage from one stage to the other being symbolically activated ('sacralised' to use a modern term) by initiation rites (*infra*). This continuous aspect explains why X signs are often represented in line (on top of each other), side by side or both simultaneously, *i.e.*, in a grid or net pattern.

Fig. 2 The regenerative principle as an X shape, according to the decorative arrangement of Çatalhöyük houses. 'Alliance' stands for the sexual mates sent to each other by each moiety (after Forest 1993: 10, Fig. 3).

It can be noted that the decorated houses of Çatalhöyük may themselves be conceived as the regenerative principle, their volume arguably embodying the pregnant womb of the lineage (hence the symbolic aura surrounding the door and threshold in traditional societies, *infra*). The fact that the unifying mates are represented on the N and S walls finds an interesting archaeological repercussion: in the map of Çatalhöyük provided by Hodder (2012: 264, Fig. 1) and Orton *et al.* (2018: 613, Fig. 1), the (Eastern) mound is divided into North and South hills separated by a trough, most befitting a separation between the dwelling areas of two exchanging moieties. This pattern will be repeated in the western Chalcolithic

mount; analogous settlement patterns have been observed in Southern Levant and Western Anatolia (Mithen *et al.* 2011: 354; Schoop 2005: 49) and are likely to be even more widespread.

Finally, the ‘H’ sign on several Göbekli Tepe steles emphasises the two parallel exchanging moieties, the unifying horizontal bar embodying their fertile union, sometimes explicitly designated with a hollowed circle immediately adjacent. The point of intersection appears like a ‘singularity’ (in the mathematical sense of the term), where the rules generally governing space and time (the ‘sacred’, exclusive, ‘unity’ of each moiety) are challenged, “an ‘escape from time’ comparable to the ‘emergence from time’ effected by myths” says Eliade (1959: 205; see also 1991: 33). Indeed, this interaction, the exogamic marriage, represents the only space-time where the two separated moieties can and must unify for the perpetuation of the whole. As argued in Bodet (2022, 2023), it is possibly this singularity that is materialised in the conspicuous (feminine?) void between the huge (male) twin steles at the centre of each Göbekli Tepe III circle and in many communal places all over the Neolithic Southwest Asia.

Grammar and Vocabulary

For societies with strict social regulations to be imposed over generations yet deprived of any writing system to express them, animal species and natural or geometric elements are selected to represent particular concepts, articulated with each other to build up a broader message. This message coded in the pre-historic symbolism has a logical syntax, recalling that found in written language texts: there is a central action (the verb), acting upon and set in motion by entities (subjects and objects), clauses with conjunctions and adjectives, substitutive and emphasising technics (*pars per toto*, suggestive blanks), as well as numbers.

The Verb

The perpetual exogamic regeneration of the society is the central action represented in the symbolic message. It is conceptualised as a feminine ‘principle’ giving life (beneficent aspect) and eventually taking it back (maleficent aspect) by unifying mates from two exogamic lineages.

The most explicit figurative representations of this principle are certain reliefs modelled on walls and similar statuettes from Çatalhöyük, where it takes the form of a parturient female figure, as Gimbutas (1989: 102-7; 141-5) noted in her paragraphs on “Exposed vulva and birth giving posture” and ‘The Pregnant Goddess’. Before its analysis, a point must be made about ‘her’ head, which Mellaart (1967: 116) says to be constantly “lost” or “defaced” and from which only

the “outline of the plaster could still be traced”. On nearly all the walls for which Mellaart provides a reconstitution, this outline looks much like a feline head, with “two small horns” (*ibid.* p. 110), arguably indicating the animal’s pointed ears. About ‘Shrine VI.44’ in particular, Mellaart (*ibid.* p. 118) writes “... whereas in many buildings the goddess is shown in person, her presence is here expressed in a life-size plaster relief of her attributes, a pair of leopards”, which implies that feline representation could easily replace or stand for this female figure. A stamp from the same site likewise shows a similarly splayed figure with two similar pointed ears (*infra*, Fig. 29) whose face is that of a carnivorous animal, maybe a bear (Hodder 2012: 275, Fig. 19). The discovery of the Sayburç relief (below), where the anthropomorphic (ithyphallic) figure has a head featuring a feline muzzle with pointed ears further supports the idea that fertile figures are often adorned with carnivorous heads. Indeed, according to Marler and Harmann (2007), because life necessarily implies its complementary corollary, death, mothers and carnivorous animals like bears are often related in archaeological and ethnographic depictions. Meskell (2017: 15) subsequently draws a connection between the (broken or detachable) heads and death for the female figures of Çatalhöyük about which McCarther (2007: 160) notes that “archaeologists now think that the head is, in fact, a skull”. Whether a skull, a carnivorous muzzle or a void left by destruction, there is little doubt that the head of the parturient figure is a symbolic representation of death, which is precisely what is expected to be found at that very place, according to Forest’s reconstruction. This could explain the habit that led to the systematic and intentional destruction of the head to symbolically “deactivate” their maleficent and deleterious power (Forest 2009: 114). As mentioned above, the feminine symbol standing for the regenerative principle can be represented, alternatively or concomitantly, through its beneficent (life-giver) or maleficent (life-taker) aspect (Salomon 1991: 90; Forest 1994: 123).

Looking back at Fig. 2, we notice that the limbs of the parturient are remarkably stretched out in an exaggerated and unnatural but undoubtedly meaningful manner. Often, the limbs touch or reach out to two parallel elements, such as columns, animal pairs or geometric lines on both sides. With what is now known about the structure of these early societies, little doubt is left about the meaning of these two parallel side elements surrounding the figure: they arguably stand for the exogamic moieties (their vertical aspect emphasising their temporality, as a succession of generations, with the limbs possibly representing the lineages of each moiety).

Apart from the modelled reliefs of Çatalhöyük and numerous female figurines found in Neolithic sites

in general (*infra*), the regenerative principle does not often appear in the symbolic compositions. As for the void between the twin steles of Göbekli Tepe enclosures, the principle is then ‘conspicuous by its absence’ as noted by Mellaart (1967: 101), meaning that it is all the more present for whoever knows the general meaning. Conversely, the exaggeratedly outstretched limbs of the parturient figure are so suggestive that the exogamic elements do not always need to be represented. Wherever the female figure (which, again, has nothing to do with real women) stands alone, not even giving birth, the regeneration is nevertheless implied by her characteristic ‘exomorphic’ position. In any case, even if not there to be seen, the regenerative principle is understood to be central to all compositions.

The regeneration principle can be conceived at the same time as a ‘state verb’ and as an ‘action verb’, in the sense that it acts (through exogamy) to change the state (dead or alive) of its product (the society) or by lending it an attribute (male/ female, auspicious/ harmful). As for its geometric representation, the regenerative principle can take the shape of an intersection point in crosses, as seen above, or a circular form (disc, spiral, spherical cavity, *etc.*). The latter generally symbolically refers to the moon (the ‘eternal return’, *infra*), women’s sexual organs, the womb, the navel, pregnancy and, thus, life (Salomon 1991: 97; Tresidder 2003: 123; Gardin *et al.* 2006: 127, 573; Yakar 2016: 174-176; Haland 2017: 166).

Subjects and Objects

The engendering principle (the ‘verb’) ‘transforms’ ascending into descending generations by unifying two dualist moieties. A set of symbols represents each of these four elements.

1) Ascending generations, that is, Death, is represented through three aspects: a) physical death, b) spiritual afterlife, and c) both; similar differentiations are pretty common in many belief systems, *e.g.*, Hinduism (Grossato 2000: 33-4).

a) Physical death is usually represented by carnivorous animals baring their teeth to emphasise the act of devouring or destroying, as we saw. However, these animals are sometimes reduced to their skin (leopard) or claws, with the same deathly connotation (Chevalier and Gheerbrant 1982: 491; Grossato 2000: 33-34; Tresidder 2000: 16; 2003: 94; Hodder and Meskell 2011: 24).

b) Spiritual afterlife is generally represented by ‘psychopomp’ birds, standing for the soul escaping or ‘flying’ from the body (at death or in a trance), a belief quite common among traditional societies (Vitebsky 1995: 13-14). The bird is often from a migrating species like crane, emphasising the cyclical nature of life, death and rebirth (Gardin *et al.* 2006: 315). This

concept of ‘Eternal Return’ (Eliade 1959: 189-195) is also transcribed in circular dances performed by shamans wearing feathered costumes in varied ethnographic records (Russell and McGowan 2003: 451-452). These migrating birds are thus likely to indicate belief in reincarnation.

c) Scavenging birds like vultures and eagles arguably combine both physical death and the spiritual afterlife (Stordeur 2003: 28; Tresidder 2003: 299; Wilson 2020: 79). According to Russell and McGowan (2003: 452) there could be a “vulture dance of death and a crane dance of life and rebirth”, while cranes could be “reborn (...) ancestors of humans” (*ibid.*: 453).

2) Descending generations, a product of the engendering principle, constitute the living society. The latter is primarily represented by the bull, often reduced to its bucranium, as we saw, thus emphasising the idea of exogamy with its set of two parallel horns (Bodet 2021: 141-143). The scorpion with its two parallel pinches (exogamy) and its tail (phallic symbol), the spider (matrimonial network) as well as, in architecture, the stone circle inserted with side steles (the lineages) sometimes embody the same social entity, each with specific connotations, as will become clear later.

3 and 4) The idea of exogamic subgroups, like moieties, sections or lineages, infuse all the elements displayed in an isomorphic arrangement, that is, in pairs of two distinct but equal and parallel entities (Bodet 2022: 14-15, 2023: 103-110). It may take the form of 1) horns of the bucranium; 2) twin steles/ pillars/ columns; 3) sets of parallel lines, whether vertical or zigzagging, painted, carved or incised; 4) set of two antithetic, converging or parallel animals (Mellaart 1967: 107, Fig.20).

We saw that because one cannot exist without the other, the product can easily replace the principle and the principle can suggest its product. Equally, the interchangeable exogamic moieties may take the place of the producer and the product simultaneously. The male society only exists because it was engendered by the feminine principle, which, in turn, only exists through its product, *etc.* Again, natural symbols are mobilised to show the fertile nature of complementary oppositions (male/ female, death/ life, summer/ winter, day/ night, sky/ earth, east/ west, *etc.*). But at last instance, they are here to emphasise the complementary opposition that matters for the perpetuation of the community through the interaction of the exogamic moieties, the only one which can ensure the life-giving reciprocal exchange of mates.

The snake is another familiar actor of the message. By its shape, it is likely to evoke the lineage, that is, a part of the society as a succession of generations through time (Forest 2006: 134). The two intertwined snakes of the Greek caduceus and other Hindu symbols, also of importance in the ‘collective

unconscious' of the Jungian school (Henderson 1964: 155; Jung 1964: 17-27; Tresidder 2003: 35), are probably a late reminiscence of the two exogamic lineages at the origin of social life. In the NSL, snakes often appear in parallel pairs as well. They are schematic, zigzagging at a right angle, a position which "suggests motion" as Benz and Bauer (2015: 4) note; the motion in question is reciprocal in nature, one lineage arguably sending (protrusion) and receiving (intrusion) mates to/ from one another at every generation.

These zigzags give meaning to the numerous broken lines, chevrons and triangles of the Neolithic repertoire: according to Forest (1993: 22), they all seem to indicate a specific direction taken by mates sent from one lineage to the other. Certain anthropomorphic representations feature eye-catching chevron-shaped arms or chevron motifs on their chest. Surprisingly, similar figures are known from rock paintings of Aborigines and Maoris, for whom it is reported to represent a mythical ancestor²/ protector of the Dream Time (Gibson 2009: 236-237). The same body disposition (splayed chevron-shaped limbs) of figures with animal heads (therianthropic) giving birth to pairs of parallel lines meandering at a right angle is also seen in several depictions of extant African Khoisan or Hadza communities, which Knight *et al.* (1995: 93-96, Figs. 7-9) link to menarchal rituals, that is, fertility.

Conjunctions and Adjectives

Certain symbols are less common but add essential connotations to the general message.

The spider probably ought to be understood as the (feminine) regenerative principle, producer and organiser of the exogamic matrimonial network, the receptacle binding together the exogamic subsections of the entire tribe throughout time (Bodet 2021: 113). Her two rows of parallel and chevron-shaped legs endorse this interpretation.

The scorpion appears as the fertile exogamic principle, the male equivalent of the spider. According to White (2014: 28), Van Bakel³ and Forest (2006: 134), the scorpion's raised stinger is a phallic symbol, while dualism is indicated by the two claws aligned with the two rows of chevron-shaped legs (like the spider).

The spider's net symbolises the endless cycle of birth, life, death and rebirth/ reincarnation in Tibetan Buddhism (Yakar 2016: 176). According to Gimbutas (1989: 81), "the intimacy of the net with the pubic triangle, uterus, and egg suggests it symbolizes an embryonic substance capable of giving life". According to Vitebsky (1995: 14), there is a belief among native Canadians that such a network of souls unites the living and the dead. More particularly here,

it appears to express the solidity and omnipresence of the 'matrimonial network', that is, the pre-arranged marital template according to which the spider (the engendering principle) organises the systematic exchange of mates for the smooth perpetuity of the society (Bodet 2021: 144-145). This idea is quite explicit on a Göbekli Tepe stele (*infra*) where the lines of the net are made of intertwined snakes, interpreted as lineages, the regular points of junction standing for the 'alliance' (union, matrimony) between them.

The *kilim* pattern may lend a temporal or multigenerational dimension to the meaning enclosed in the net, but these two are essentially similar. Considering that diamonds are a "stylised representation of the vulva (...), a life principle", according to Tresidder (2003: 6), the kilim pattern is then nothing but a succession of diamonds on top and the side of each other, that is, an image of the successive generations (vertical lines) of exogamic lineages (horizontal lines) through time and space (Forest 1993: 21-31).

The square or the rectangle, generally interpreted as a symbol of stability, strength and completeness as it encompasses "the four corners of the world" (Gibson 2009: 9), could stand for the strength of the society, but also as a finite entity, that of its interrelated individuals. For pre-state people, the society *is* the world (Barnard 1978; 2020: 47-51). In the Warlis culture (India), the 'mother goddess' occupies a 'Devchawk' or 'sacred' square enclosure' (Yakar 2016: 176). Consequently, squares and rectangles could refer to the larger society (in particular in the sense of a confined matrimonial network), possibly extending from one generation to the next when these shapes are represented on top of each other or, hypothetically, as endogamous societies living side by side, when represented next to each other.

Repeated geometric figures, as found in net or kilim patterns, interestingly recall the anthropologists' schematic representations of the kinship patterns of traditional tribes, generally implying the marriage of 'cross-cousins'⁴ (Walker *et al.* 2011; Frazer 1910: vol. IV). More precisely, they appear as a representation of what Lévi-Strauss calls the 'generalised' type of alliance pattern (Bodet 2012), in which all *exogamic* lineages are bound together, one to the next, and the last to the first, in a larger, yet closed, matrimonial circle, making up the entire *endogamous* tribe. Even though in Çatalhöyük the context differs somehow (Chyleński *et al.* 2019) – as the agglutinative architecture infers the probable kidnapping of outsider women (Forest 1996a: 5, 2006: 131) –, genetic research in Basta, for example, has largely confirmed the existence of such local endogamous situations (Alt *et al.* 2013: 1). Though the 'generalised' kinship

pattern includes several exchanging lineages, the fundamental concept of exogamy remains central.

Finally, a very similar symbol, 'Ø', found both on Göbekli Tepe steles and on the chest of an Aboriginal medicine man (Notroff 2017) as well as on their cave paintings (Anati 2003: 307), is symptomatic. Together with crosses, splayed limbs or parallel zigzags, which are even more common in the iconography of traditional communities, this uniformity of the motifs chosen around the globe shows not only the universality of the exogamic principle but also the reduced number of possible ways to express it figuratively.

Emphasis and Substitutions: 'Pars pro Toto' and 'Suggestive Blanks'

Pars pro toto: this technique, whereby one significant detail stands for the whole element, as a shortcut or as a way to emphasise the former (Grossato 2000: 38-39), is widespread in the NSL. We mentioned that the bucranium stood for the bull, the latter representing the society as the strong unity, the former emphasising the exogamic infrastructure of the latter with the two parallel horns (Bodet 2021). Deer antlers have a particular connotation, with branches spurring out regularly from the main trunk, arguably referring to (the mates from) the distinct lineages spurring out regularly from the main trunk (the society as a whole), generation after generation. In contrast, their regular falling and renewal would refer to the 'eternal return' (Grossato 2000: 138). This technique also functions the other way around (*toto pro pars*), where the larger element, like the bull or a feline, implies a detail, respectively the bucranium or the teeth, symbols of exogamy and physical death.

Bucrania can be found alone, in front of the entrance of a communal building, displayed in the central area of the village (e.g., at Hallan Çemi, Rosenberg and Redding 2002: 45-49), or in ceremonial or burial contexts in Northern and Southern Levant (Coqueugniot 2000: 69-71; Goring-Morris and Horwitz 2007: 914; Goring-Morris and Belfer-Cohen 2011: 64-66). Caches of horn cores, including of gazelle, are placed over the head of human burials in Jordan's Azraq Basin already in the Epipalaeolithic (Maher and Macdonald 2022: 50). In each case, there is little doubt that, in the eyes of the prehistoric spectator, the exogamic principle is suggested by this simple object. We also saw that the pivotal concepts of the NSL are complementary and that antithetic elements like life and death or the two moieties often stand for one another. The living society can thus easily be represented by a deathly element, similar to the Buddha being "engendered by his mouth" (Eliade 1959: 199-200) or to the Greek Caryatids, which, according to Casabone (2023:59), symbolise the

concept of "reversibility of life and death". This apparent contradiction also finds its logic in the 'eternal return' (*infra*).

'Suggestive blanks' strongly indicate the presence of features that are not explicitly represented but are well-known from other, more complete versions. We saw how, in Çatalhöyük, the splayed arms of the parturient female suggest by themselves the exogamic moieties, while in Göbekli Tepe, the substantial twin steles are separated by a void probably suggesting the regenerative principle, a symbolic passage from life to death and *vice versa* (Bodet 2022: 14). In fact, most figurative representations have suggestive blanks because it is challenging to have the entire message pictured in one image, contrary to geometric signs like the cross. In any case, the missing element is 'conspicuous by its absence', at least for the initiated. Indeed, there is a possibility that adolescents may be taught how to 'read' the iconography during their initiation ceremony, similar to the situation found among the Baruyas (Godelier 1996: 61-89), where mythical knowledge acted as a differentiation between the initiated and the uninitiated.

Another way to emphasise a particular feature is to represent it on a proportionally larger scale and/or from a different perspective than the rest of the body: bucrania are often represented from above, while the bull's body (together with the heads of all other animals) is in profile.

Numbers

The NSL has three primary numbers: one, two, and multitude; a few subsidiary ones, notably three, also occasionally appear.

a) The number 'two' is most fundamental; it contains in itself the founding 'dualist scheme' of the prehistoric ideology (Testart 1985: 477-490; Bodet 2022: 16-18), the primordial and original differentiation which every traditional community is careful to preserve. It is most conspicuous with the monumental parallel steles found in the centre of communal buildings all over Southwest Asia (Bodet 2023: 101-8), as well as in a long series of isomorphic or antithetic animal and human figures or vertical lines in the iconography as we will see.

b) In the central compositions, duality shares the central space with unity, with which is in a complementary relation. There is *one dualist* principle (the 'exomorphic' parturient female figure in particular), producing *one dualist* society (the male product/ stele). The unity of the society is dependent on its primordial division, but duality makes sense as the essence of the unity; in other words, it takes two exogamic subgroups to make up one endogamous society. The complementarity between 'unity' and 'duality' is found in Göbekli Tepe III, where the stone circle surrounding

each ‘unique’ enclosure is arguably *the* (one) product of the ‘dualist’ principle represented by one set of twin steles in its centre (Bodet 2022).

c) The number three appears in at least four of the pictures analysed here. In one case, three bucrania are superimposed and likely stand for the concept of filiation, as indicated by the small calf head just above them (Forest 1993: 5-6). In the other cases, the three elements (respectively snakes, rectangular shapes and X-shaped figures) are placed side by side. There, though this interpretation is highly debatable and open to discussion, their systematic isomorphic disposition seems to refer to the contraction of a) and b), where two moieties make up one society ($2+1=3$); in other words, the two parallel side moieties could be depicted in the process of merging in the centre to constitute the ‘one exogamic’ society.

d) More than three is ‘multitude’, understood in its spatial (omnipresent) and temporal (successive generations) terms: it can be the totality of the swapped individuals (past, present and future) making up the society, as well as the multiple hunters probably standing for death surrounding society (Forest 1993: 5-6). Rarely a specific plural number is expressly designated, like the 4, 8 or 12 side steles inserted in Göbekli Tepe and Nevalı Çori enclosures, the snakes depicted in the net pattern or the series of snakeheads on top of each other on several steles. In these cases, these numbers may stand for the sub-sections of the (endogamous) tribe, engaged in a generalised type of kinship pattern, exchanging mates with each other in a regular pattern (A to B, B to C, ... back to A).

If the latter hypothesis happens to be correct, every circle in Göbekli could represent one tribe (1 circle), the temporal result of countless (multiple) generations and the spatial configuration of several (4, 8 or 12) subsections produced by the regenerative exogamic principle embodied in two (2) abstract moieties, the central twin steles. In other words, *all* the lineages (multiple) shall remain bound as *one* (1) strong society as long as they respect the ‘complementary opposition’ of the *dualist* principle (2).

Complementary Oppositions

The importance attached to exogamy explains the visceral fear that all prime societies may lose the primordial differentiation and fall into an unsustainable, undifferentiated world (Girard 1972: 248) without clearly defined subsections. This is why the ‘complementary opposition’, the essential precondition of the exogamic principle, is represented as ‘natural’ as the opposition between day and night, east and west, summer and winter, and life and death. Suppose the moon is a widespread symbol for the “eternal return” concept. In that case, it is because a

black moon is invariably followed by a new moon: “the moon reveals (...) that a new birth always follows death”; it is thus “a reconciliation of contraries”, says Eliade (1959: 156). This complementary opposition entails the representation at once of the regenerative principle both through its beneficent (life-giving) and maleficent (life-taking) aspects (Eliade 1959: 172-175; 1991: 49; Benz and Bauer 2015: 7-9), hence the *vagina dentata* or toothed vagina, present in many traditional cultures (Devereux 1983: 168; Salomon 1991: 66, 89; Ross 2021). Often, only one of these aspects is represented (generally the deathly one), but the opposite aspect, again, is systematically implied.

In the Neolithic symbolism, there are thence two interchangeable couples of oppositions (life and death, the two exogamic moieties), expressed on the same symbolic plan (Fig. 1). However, because life and death are natural phenomena on which humans have no or little control, only the second couple (exogamic moieties) is significant in the message, under the form of a warning: ‘the entire community (1) is at stake if individuals (mult.) do not respect the primordial social division (2)’. The social and economic context triggering such a fear, specifically in the Neolithic period, is undoubtedly due to the advent of the farming mode of production, which requires marital unions outside the tribe (*infra*, Forest 1996b; Bodet 2019a: 39-43, 2022: 15-16).

Glossary: a ‘Neolithic Sign List’

“Expressing mystical primordial thoughts encoded in symbols goes back to the Palaeolithic period”, writes Yakar (2016: 168-169), who mentions a system of up to 26 symbols including circles, net patterns, zigzags or lines constituting “the earliest form of written language, best defined as a language of symbols”. The latter is equally recognised by Anati (2003: 370-385), who discussed the ‘elementary structure of prehistoric art’ logically arranged as a series of pictograms, ideograms and psychograms according to a definable ‘associative mechanism’ centred around the essential horse-bison couple (of the Upper Palaeolithic Franco-Cantabrian cave paintings). The same set of signs was standard in Neolithic Northern Mesopotamia’s symbolism and the Levant (Mithen *et al.* 2023: 834). About the “basic bipartition, common to the entire Franco-Cantabrian art”, Cauvin (1997: 101) further states that “if the symbolic ‘grammar’ seems common to all (the caves), the vocabulary is not so, and the precise signification is far from clear”. If the first clause of this sentence is generally neglected though immensely important (as detailed above), the second must now be reviewed. Even though Forest’s 1993 article appears in Cauvin’s bibliography, it was not given much consideration as it is not discussed in the text.

What needed to be added to these researchers in decoding the basic meaning structuring this prehistoric symbolic language is the universal dualist ideology as analysed by the ethnologist Testart (1985). By applying the latter’s results, Forest (1993, 2006) could assign specific meanings to most compositions of Catalhöyük.

Below is a list of about 20 figurative and geometric symbols appearing in the NSL with their assumed meaning (and emphasised connotation in parenthesis). It is compiled from Forest’s (1993, 2003, 2006) interpretations of Neolithic symbolism to which the author (Bodet 2021, 2022, 2023), following the same system, added a few precisions deriving mainly from the symbolism of Göbekli and the Levant (the net and spider, the H sign, the square, the bucranium, *etc.*). This glossary will help follow the decipherment of the compositions proposed in the last section of this article after this brief methodological clarification:

Signs are ‘selected’ over time for their ability to represent a particular concept (hence the spider producing the marital ‘network’, for example). However, when the list below is read bluntly, the meaning attached to those symbols may seem to the reader as mere guesswork. Though most ‘translations’ are backed up with ethnographic references, this scepticism is a common and legitimate reaction, shared by the author himself upon reading Forest for the first time. The main reason for this comes from the fact that the concepts mobilised (first and foremost, ‘exogamy’) do not have the same, if any, repercussions in modern society. This is precisely why it was necessary to start this investigation by presenting the social context of these ideograms, thereby responding to the question: “what symbols would a society choose if it didn’t have writing but desired to express the concepts of exogamy, regeneration, (physical/spiritual) death, lineage *etc.*?” The emergence of symbols is a long-term process, but, as mentioned above, it remains fascinating that roughly the same sets of images have been widely selected by traditional cultures (past and extant) across the globe to embody similar meanings.

Still, the only way to truly convince the reader of the possible accuracy of these ‘translations’ is the proof by repetition. It will be done by showing that the particular meaning allocated to every specific symbol (with inevitable nuances here and there) systematically produces a variant of the same coherent message, over and over again. The aim is to remove gradually the probability of coincidences. This is why this ‘glossary’ is followed by the ‘translation’ (and a brief analysis when needed) of more than 70 depictions of the Neolithic repertoire, from the most straightforward to the most intricate conceptual representations. First, it should become clear that nothing is random but preconceived to produce meaning, and second, that the

exogamic principle unifies them all. Even if exogamy alone cannot reveal the meaning of all the details enclosed in these images, it appears as a fundamentally structuring basis. Beyond the mere translations, the ultimate aim is to show that the meanings delivered are generally in tune with the social context devised above, opening a window into these communities’ ideology. This can be conceived as a materialisation of Lévi-Strauss’ (1958) search for the fundamental sociocultural prehistoric structure that, beyond cultural differences, universally binds individuals by sharing a body of symbols (Yakar 2016: 166-167).

Geometric Ideograms

	Regenerative principle transforming ascending generations -death- into descending ones -life- (vertical axis), through the interaction of two exogamic moieties (horizontal axis)
	Exogamic principle, emphasizing on the separate, parallel and equal moieties (vertical bars) uniting only through exogamic alliance (thin horizontal trait)
	Fertility, maternal womb, feminine sexual organs
	Fecund interaction of two moieties
	Lineage sending and receiving mates
	Mate (male) going from one moiety/ matrilineage to the other for alliance (marriage)
	Repetition of the above over generations
	Socially circumscribed strength of a moiety/ of the society as a whole
	Generation waning from birth (top point) until puberty (right and left points/ intercourse with other lineages), and waxing until death (bottom point). The diamond can be read as two sets of two bounded triangles superimposed on each other in the same figure.
	Kilim pattern: the society in time, as a succession of exogamic generations
	Net/ grid = the society as a social fabric and a preformed marital network

Figurative Ideograms

- the (parturient) female figure = the (female) regenerative principle
- the bull = the (male) society // bucranium = exogamic moieties // single horn = the lineage
- the carnivorous animal (teeth, skin, claws) = physical death / ascending generations
- the psychopomp bird = soul’s afterlife (flying from the dead body)
- the scavenging bird = both physical and psychopomp death

- the migrating bird = the eternal return (from life to death, back and forth)
- the (zigzagging) snake = the lineage as a succession of generations (exchanging mates)
- the spider (chevron legs in opposed direction) = feminine builder of the society's marital network
- the scorpion (sting, opposed legs/claws) = male and exogamic regenerative principle (and its product)
- the steles (pillar)/ columns = the moieties (2) or lineages (4, 8, 12) of the society as a whole
- the (chevron-splayed/ crossed) human arms/ fingers = exchanging moieties/ lineages/ individual mates

Deciphered Images

Enough is known now about the general structure of the NSL, its symbols and the overall conveyed message to start 'reading' and 'translating' several depictions. We will begin with 'compositions', which are representations with more than one element because it is the repetition of the same associations between individual components that induce the meaning assigned to each of them in the sign list above. More than 40 such figurative compositions will be reviewed, subsequently allowing to assign, with a certain degree of confidence, a meaning to nearly as many isolated motifs and geometric depictions.

The different compositions have been roughly classified under four main types following the primary connotation emphasised in each case: *'the regenerative principle is exogamic'*, *'society stems from reciprocal moieties'*, *'the exogamic society is stronger than death'* and *'the engendering principle under its deleterious affect'*. However, the reader should not lend more importance to this division than it deserves, as it is more here to help structure *our* reading than to reveal *their* intentions. It will become clear that all depictions overlap largely, with an inevitable redundancy from one picture to the next.

Occurrences of symbols related to the NSL, most in the form of simple geometric or schematic depictions, are prevalent all over Anatolia and Northern Mesopotamia (Fig. 3). However, the majority of the figurative depictions analysed here and on which our decipherment of the symbolic system relies, derive from the same three sites: Çatalhöyük, Göbekli Tepe III (PPNA) and II (PPNB), and Nevalı Çori. The pictures (or depictions) discussed here are numbered 1 to 75 and referred to as 'Pic.' when mentioned in the text (*i.e.*, 'Pic. 12'). The photographs or drawings of nearly 30 of them are reproduced here to illustrate the text, and are referred to as 'Fig.' Factual translations are provided between single 'inverted commas', the correlation in the depicted features between parenthesis, and suggested meanings are given within square brackets.

"The Regenerative Principle is Exogamic"

About a dozen compositions featuring parturient figures, generally explicitly depicted in the birthing process, were recovered at Çatalhöyük by Mellaart (1967: 102-103, Fig. 16), usually painted on the western walls of houses over several layers. They are here presented from the most complete to the simplest and schematic forms so that the meaning encoded in the suggestive blanks gradually appears. The Shrine number is indicated to match each picture with its sketch drawing in Fig. 4 (references for detailed reconstructions are given when applicable).

1 - 2) The parturient reliefs (Fig. 5), Çatalhöyük - VI.A.10 and VI.B.10 (Mellaart 1967: 46, 124, 127-129, Figs. 38 and 40): on the west wall of Shrines VIA and B, the splayed female figure (with a destroyed but arguably originally feline head) is giving birth to three superimposed bucrania topped by a smaller one. Her legs are supported by two vertical, parallel, symbolic⁵ columns, placed precisely on either side of (thus reduplicating) the horns of the three bucrania (as if the columns were joined by the tips of each horn). The calf head on top arguably underlines the affiliation between the feminine principle and the three 'males' below. Forest's interpretation (1993: 3-4, 7, 2003: 43) can be summarised in these terms: 'the regenerative principle [devours ascending generations (feline head) and] engenders (three/ several) new generations one after the other (calf and bucrania) through the unification of the two exogamic moieties/ lineages (the parallel vertical columns) composing the community as a whole'.

3) The splayed parturient above two superimposed bucrania, Çatalhöyük - VI.31: this is the same depiction as the previous one without the vertical pillars, which are suggested by the outstretched limbs reduplicating the horns of the bucrania below. Whether two or three bucrania are depicted probably matters little; the idea of repetition seems to be expressed here. This position implies here again a relationship of filiation between the principle and the engendered bucrania as if the exogamic nature of the principle (the parturient) was passed on to the delivered generations: 'the exogamic female principle engenders exogamic male generations one after the other'.

4-5) The splayed parturient above a bucranium, Çatalhöyük - VIA.8 and VIB.8 (Mellaart 1967: 124, Fig. 37): the twin columns (moieties) are again absent but suggested by the splayed arrangement of the figure = 'the society as a whole (the bull) is engendered by the exogamic (splayed) principle'.

6) The parturient splayed between two columns, Çatalhöyük - VII.45 (*ibid.*: 115, Fig. 27): the limbs of the figure (outline of a feline head?) are reaching out to two vertical pillars. Here, the bull is absent but suggested by the posture = 'the principle [destroys

Fig. 3 Sites with figurative and/ or geometric signs of the Neolithic Symbolic Language (NSL).

Fig. 4 The main 'shrine' decorations, Çatalhöyük by Mellaart 1967: 102-103, Fig. 16. (with kind permission by A. Mellaart)

Fig. 5 Reconstruction of Shrine VI.B.10, West Wall. Çatalhöyük. (reconstructed in Mellaart 1967, 125, Fig. 38; with kind permission by A. Mellaart)

(feline head) and] engenders the society by ensuring the junction between the two moieties of the society’
7-8) The splayed parturient alone, Çatalhöyük - VII.23 and VII.31 (*ibid.*: 115, Fig. 28): the figure is alone but the limbs are stretched in the same exaggerated manner as those of the figures described above. This is enough to suggest the presence of both the parallel columns and the bull = ‘the regenerative exogamic (splayed) principle [engenders the society by unifying its two moieties]’.

9) Two anthropomorphic figures side-by-side above one bucranium, Çatalhöyük - VII.I: depicted frontally, the adjacent limbs of both figures reach out to each other. In contrast, the outer limbs reach out to a bull plastered in profile on both sides. The “twin goddess figures are by no means rare”, says Mellaart (*ibid.*: 110-1), but, here, are they really twin? Looking at a detailed drawing on page 109, Fig. 23, contrarily to the sketch drawing in Fig. 3, which misleadingly places the bull *between* the two parturient figures, only one of the figures engenders (the left one), and it is the only one with breasts. Hypothetically, this may be read as ‘the society (the bucranium) is engendered by the intercourse of mates (limbs of the anthropomorphic figures) sent by each of the two moieties (the side bulls), but filiation is matrilineal’ (which Forest 1993: 2 indeed supposes more likely to be the case than a patrilineal one for Neolithic societies).

10) The two schematic parturient figures (Fig. 6), Çatalhöyük - VI.14 (*ibid.*: 120, Fig. 32): the composition is very similar to the previous picture, but the figures are represented by two rectangular spaces (equal and complementary exogamic moieties?) delineated by two vertical columns and joined by a central one (the continuation of the society in time?). A bucranium, topped by a smaller ram head (filiation),

is placed below the right-hand rectangle, the two delineating columns prolonging exactly the two horns = ‘the junction of two equal and strictly delineated moieties engenders the exogamic society (calf/ bucranium)’.

11) A “huge bull’s head, surmounting a red-painted niche” (Mellaart 1967: 48, Fig. 28), Çatalhöyük - VI.10: the niche is placed between two small columns truncated precisely where the horn cores are found. Red, symbolising blood, is related to life and death, as well as with dualism and exogamy according to Testart (1985: 451-476), and the cavity may be reminiscent of a pregnant womb = ‘the feminine regenerative principle (the niche) and the society (the bull’s head) which it engenders are respectively *framed* and *supported* by the two exogamic societies (the columns)’.

Fig. 6. Reconstruction of ‘Shrine VI.14’. Çatalhöyük. The union in time (the central column) of the two moieties (the two rectangles) gives birth to a new generation (the ram) of the same exogamic society (the bull). (Reconstructed in Mellaart 1967: 120, Fig. 32; with kind permission by A. Mellaart)

12) The “Mistress of animals” clay statuette (Fig. 7), Çatalhöyük (*ibid.*: 139, Fig. 67; 156-157, Plate IX): a sitting female figure is giving birth (to a male child or a calf?) by putting her hands on two symmetrical leopard heads topping vertical elements alongside her legs (armrests), probable symbols of the two exogamic moieties represented under their deathly aspect (ascending generations). All five elements of the

exogamic message delivered in the cross in Fig. 1 are present in this figurine. The two exogamic moieties (4+5: the two vertical armrests) are unified by the regenerative principle (1: the female body), which destroys the ascending generations (2: the leopards and probably the deliberately broken head), giving birth to descending generations (3: calf or baby). In addition, the hands petting the leopards convey an idea of submission, as if the life principle (of the society) was simultaneously the ‘mistress’ of death (Forest 2009: 114). This theme of death controlled by exogamy will be further illustrated below.

Fig. 7 Clay figurine (approx. 20cm in height). Çatalhöyük. The regenerating principle is giving birth by joining two moieties represented under their deathly aspect (leopards). (from Mellaart 1967: 184, Fig. 52; with kind permission by A. Mellaart)

13) The splayed incised female (Fig. 8), Göbekli Tepe II (Hauptmann 1999: 55, Fig. 35): legs, breasts and arms of the figure are splayed in such an unnatural position that it appears to be made of two profiles glued into one frontal body. This is especially true for the head (which has nothing anthropomorphic), the two ‘faces’ looking in opposite directions. Limbs are bent in a characteristic chevron pattern, arguably standing for mates moving from one moiety to the other (Forest 1993: 22; see Pics. 13-4, 23-4, 51-2). ‘She’ seems to be giving birth, maybe to a (couple(?) of) leopard-clawed paws (symbol of death), a phallic sign maybe suggesting at the same time the life-giving sexual intercourse (?). ‘Every life, and thus every death (the paw) delivered by the regenerative principle implies an exogamic exchange and union

between two distinct moieties’ (for more details, see Bodet 2021: 147-149, Fig. 6).

Fig. 8 The two-profile-headed splayed female figure (approx. 30cm in height). Göbekli Tepe II. (Urfa Museum, Photo: P. Torres, licenced under CC BY-NC-SA 2.0)

14) The tortoise limestone carving (Fig. 9), Nevalı Çori (Hauptmann 1999: 48, Fig. 16; 2007: 127, Fig. 16). Symbol of long life in several traditions (Gibson 2009: 131, 9; Gardin *et al.* 2006: 617), the tortoise is depicted between a man and a woman, all displayed frontally and joining hands in a characteristic XXX pattern = ‘the intercourse of mates from distinct moieties ensures the long life (of the society)’. The depiction of the regenerative figure as an animal (spiders, scorpions, snakes, bulls) is not rare (*infra*).

15) The vulture-beaked crosses with an anthropomorphic figure, stone bowl (Fig. 10), from Körtik Tepe (Özkaya and San 2007: 23, Fig. 17): the crosses seem to represent the regenerative principle joining two parallel snakes zigzagging at a right angle on either side (probably standing for the exogamic lineages). The crosses thus seem to symbolise the regenerative principle unifying two lineages/ snakes (with the horizontal bar of the cross), allowing the cyclical passage of generations from death to life and *vice versa* (vertical bar). The superimposed crosses, repeated around the surface of the bowl in sets of two,

are topped by a protrusion (alternatively to the right and the left) in the shape of a schematic bird (Benz and Bauer 2015: 4): death (the ascending generations), here as well, is represented at the top end of cruciform motifs. Just like the houses of Çatalhöyük⁶, where death motifs are depicted on eastern walls and life on western walls, crosses on Körtik bowls operate in a direction opposite to that of life. ‘The exogamic beaks (alternatively right and left) first swallow ascending generations for the exogamic principle (horizontal line of the cross) to deliver new ones (lower part of the cross)’.

Fig. 9 The XXX tortoise composition (approx. 13.5cm in height). Fragment of a stone vessel. Nevalı Çori. (“Urfa Museum, Neolithic age 4794” by Dosseman, licenced under CC BY-SA 4.0)

On the same bowl, between the two beaked crosses and a zigzagging snake, appears an anthropomorphic figure with splayed limbs (Benz and Bauer 2015: 3, Figs. 2-3). It is highly schematic, wearing a garment with a net pattern while the head is made of two concentric circles and two parallel antennae. This figure appears as the personification of a matrimonially stable (net-work) and splayed (exogamic) entity, arguably, the society as a whole. Then, here, the engendering principle (the beaked cross) would be represented side by side with its product, the society (the anthropomorphic figure).

16) Small plain female figurines are recovered in a large number of Neolithic sites all over Southwest Asia (Aurenche and Kozłowski 1999: 117-119); hundreds of them were found at Höyücek and other sites of Western Anatolia (Duru 2012: 11, 49, Fig. 46). Recovered in or around houses, they were discarded in middens, open areas and empty spaces between buildings. These figurines are very ordinary and mundane, the quality and detail of execution being given little importance. They notably inspired J. Cauvin for his theory on the spiritual origin of agriculture (1997: 50-54, 99-102), but the term ‘goddess’, often employed to describe them, is not only in contradiction with their poor quality and context of findings but does not make sociological

sense within a pre-state organisation (Testart 2006: 22). It is only a few millennia later that the prehistoric *regenerative principle* will take the form of a female ‘deity’ *per se* with the emergence of urban hierarchical social classes, organised state religion and professional priests (Forest 1996b: 133-140).

Fig. 10 Beaked crosses, Stone Bowl 67 (approx. 15cm in height). Körtik Tepe. (Drawing: aperitero CC BY-SA 4.0, from an original in Özkaya *et al.* 2013: 61; see also Özkaya and Coşkun 2013: 32).

Interestingly, the head of these small figurines, generally preserved (not broken intentionally), is usually anthropomorphic (sometimes phallic), and not that of a carnivorous animal. It seems that only the principle's positive, fertile aspect is shown, without mentioning the deathly corollary, “portable objects that incorporate agency or magical properties designed to influence people’s lives,” says Cartolano (2022: 165). These small figurines' symbolic aura and use appear purely domestic, at the nuclear family level (maybe just for the mother?).

These small figurines are distinct from the female reliefs modelled on the walls of Çatalhöyük (Pics. 1-10), from the two large stone statuettes placed in a building platform at the same site (Yalman 2021: 131-133) and even from the ‘mistress of animals’ figurine (Pic. 12). The latter group, better executed and larger, may have been considered a more valuable version of the small clay figurines, maybe ‘magically active’ for a larger kin group, at the scale of the entire lineage or the whole society. The small clay figurines kept at home may be considered cheap versions of these larger pieces. The simple act of their production, however coarsely, may express the magical wish to increase the fertility of the household, just like believers of modern religions keep in their houses small and easy-made copies of grand symbols found in

large religious buildings. Interestingly, the general absence of small female figurines at Göbekli Tepe, while abundant in nearby Nevalı Çori except in the communal ‘Kultgebäude’, supports this difference in symbolic aura between household and communal contexts. This fact also supports the idea that Göbekli Tepe was probably not simply a regular domestic settlement (Dietrich and Notroff 2015: 85).

“Society stems from reciprocal moieties”

This category applies mainly to the concepts enclosed in Göbekli Tepe’s symbolism. Contrary to the previous one, here, the analysis goes from simple to rich depictions to slowly familiarise oneself with the ‘reading’ of growingly complex compositions. The narrow sides of the steles are particularly rich and instructive. The two vertical and parallel lines generally carved along their edges are an active part of the composition, likely symbolising the two moieties as endless successions of generations.

17) The small bucranium on the narrow side of Stele 31 (Fig 11), Göbekli Tepe III (Schmidt 2007a: 204, Fig. 81). The two horns of the bucranium overlap the two vertical lines, implying a common connotation: both seem to represent the two exogamic moieties, united by the bucranium. The latter also features a round hollow between the two horns, which probably stands for the fertile principle, here activated by the interaction between the two lineages (through the intercourse of their individual mates). This bucranium then appears to contain the engendering principle, allowing for the whole’s momentary regeneration (hence the composition’s general verticality). ‘The society (the bull) engenders (the hollow) itself by the union of the lineages (the two horns) coming from the two moieties (the two vertical lines), thus allowing the exogamic society as a whole to continue in time (verticality)’. In terms of further precision: the lineage as a social entity is symbolised by a horn because it is *symbolically* considered to be male (in complementary opposition with the feminine life-giving principle), but we are here in the realm of pure abstraction; practically, the lineage is composed of both men and women, intermarrying with, respectively, women and men of other lineages. It, therefore, does not matter whether they are patri- or matrilineal, the critical thing being that they are unilineal (to designate the cross-cousins -or other relatives- to be married and perpetuate exogamy).

18) The antithetic snake / bull and fox scene (Fig. 12), narrow side of Stele 20, Enclosure D, Göbekli Tepe III (Schmidt 2007a: 206, Fig. 83). The bull is in profile, but its vast head (relative to the body) is purposely pictured from above so that the tip of each horn touches the two vertical lines, obviously making the junction between the two moieties composing the

society. The snake is zigzagging at right angles, each triangular edge alternatively touching the same vertical bands. The bull comes face-to-face with the snake. Still, more than a confrontation, this could represent the merging of the past generations that have continuously exchanged mates in time (the zigzagging snake) into the actual solid society exactly where its exogamic characteristic comes to the front (the bucranium). Also, a possible open-mouthed fox (badly damaged) was uncovered below the bull, but on a smaller scale: this arrangement may imply that the exogamic society as a whole (the bull) is stronger than the death of its individuals (fox), a recurrent theme we will encounter below. The general reading may be something like = ‘the moieties of the society continuously exchanging mates through time (the snake) engenders the actual strong society (bull), which, as long as it keeps on respecting exogamy (the bucranium), remains stronger than death (fox)’.

Fig. 11 Overlapping bucranium. Narrow side of Stele 31. Göbekli Tepe III. (Drawing: aperitero CC BY-SA 4.0, from an original DAI picture: Schmidt 2007a: 204, Fig. 81)

Fig. 12 Bull, snake and fox composition. Narrow side of Stele 20, Göbekli Tepe III. (Drawing: aperitero CC BY-SA 4.0, from an original DAI picture: Schmidt 2007b: 114, Fig. 22).

19) The narrow side of Stele 33 (Fig. 13), enc. D, Göbekli Tepe III (Schmidt 2007b: 109, Fig. 9; 2011: 65, Fig. 9). Here, the bottom part of the two vertical stripes lining the edges is made up of a series of superimposed snakeheads, 11 on one side, 12 on the other (maybe to express the idea of circular matrimonial exchange on a flat surface: see Pic. 29 for a detailed explanation). This is another strong confirmation that these vertical stripes will likely stand for the exogamic moieties. It is probably not a coincidence that the surrounding wall of Enclosure D, where this stele is inserted, is composed of 12 side steles: both snakeheads in the iconography and side steles in the architecture are indeed likely to stand for the mate-exchanging lineages making up the whole exogamic tribe. Societies of 12 exogamic subsections (like the 12 ‘tribes’ of Israel) are not rare and are even a general model used by Freud (1913 [2010: 51]) in his famous ‘Totem and Taboo’ essay. The central (fertile)

space between these two lines (the equivalent of the empty space between the central twin steles?) is filled with clear ‘exomorphic’ signs. Among them, the parallel waving snakes, the H sign, the two spiders (whose legs are in a chevron pattern, arguably standing for the exchanged partners) as well as a small bull in profile above the second spider, all explicitly making the junction between the two lines/ moieties. The waving snakes, in particular, appear as two sets of three systematically touching one vertical line after the other. The number three is unclear, but the two side snakes may reduplicate the two moieties, assisting the central one (the society as a whole) in perpetuating through time. The suggested reading = ‘the society has been advancing through time by the systematic alliance (the upper set of zigzagging snakes) between the two moieties (the two vertical side lines) until the crucial moment where the (sexual?) union of the two exogamic mates (the H sign) reproduces its fertile matrimonial network (the spider). Once the birthing process is accomplished, the exogamic society continues in time (the lower set of the three curving snakes) to keep on engendering the society (the small bull in profile) and, again, its matrimonial network (the second spider)’.

In the pictographic technique, the central H-spider couple seems to be a momentary ‘snapshot’ of the fundamental union, whereby the same eternal and systematic process of exogamic regeneration continues through time. Also, Schmidt (2007a: 214, the caption of Fig. 92) notes that the upper spider has two sets of three legs, while the lower one has two sets of four, which may be a significant detail that is not easily understandable.

20) Twin Stele 18, Enclosure D (Fig. 14), Göbekli Tepe III (Schmidt 2007b: 108, Fig. 8; 2011: 81, Fig. 32). The T-shaped stele together with its ‘twin’ are partly anthropomorphic with a rectangular ‘head’ and a human arm on each side, depicted in a very characteristic chevron pattern (‘the mates migrating from one moiety to the other’). These arms unite on the narrow side of the stele as a pair of parallel hands and fingers, possibly standing for the individual mates reciprocally sent by the two moieties to each other. The meaning of the rectangular ‘head’ of the T-shape stele is still elusive. However, it may stand for the (contemporary) society as the result of the succession of generations represented on the vertical pedestal on which it stands. On top of the narrow side (upper close-up on Fig. 14), just below the ‘head’, “there are reliefs in the shape of a crescent, a disc and a motive of two antithetic elements, whose meaning so far eludes us” wrote Klaus Schmidt (2011: 46). The exogamic principle allows us to suggest several clarifications. We first note that these two ‘antithetic elements’ are made of two rectangles aligned along and arguably reduplicating the two vertical lines of the narrow side

and extending towards each other through a thin line, like an H sign, though slightly broken in the middle, a possible allusion to the fundamental separation between the moieties. The actual union is expressed just below with the crescent (looking very much like a stylised bucranium), each tip joining the two vertical side lines (moieties), and embracing the shape of a 'hollowed disc' above, probably standing for a symbolic vulva/ womb, the generating principle itself. Attempted reading = 'the actual society (rectangular head of the T) is engendered (hollow disc) by the exogamic union (bucranium/ crescent) of the two moieties of the society (the two parallel and chevron-shaped arms depicted on both sides of the stele)'.

In the lower part of the same narrow side (visible in Fig. 14), at loin level, the side arms naturally end up with two hands, the fingers ending precisely with the vertical lines of the narrow side, confirming again that both relate to the same concept, the exogamic moieties. Placed precisely in front of and extending towards each other (see Pics. 34, 41-42), the fingers could stand for individual mates reciprocally exchanged as aforementioned. In addition, the smaller finger of both hands is unnaturally, deliberately placed on top, possibly to give a sense of the filiation, like the calf topping the three engendered bulls (Pics.1-2) in Çatalhöyük (Forest 1994: 119). Just below, a possible snake (society in time) in the shape of a crescent makes the union between the moieties (vertical side lines), where superimposed H and X exogamic signs appear precisely at this location. Inserted in the crescent snake is a half-circle featuring two incised lines (a plausible exogamic vulva symbol?). It is seemingly giving birth, below, to an animal skin, represented as a pair of clawed paws (death) placed on either side of its tail (probably a phallic symbol).

The reading of the lower part can be = 'The exchanged mates (the parallel fingers) from the lineage (arm) of each moiety (vertical side-lines) unite (the crescent snake) and give birth (incised half circle) to the male society, here shown under its deathly aspect (the animal skin/ tail/ claws), but which exogamic nature (the two parallel paws) implies the rebirth'. Tentative decipherment of the whole stele = 'reproducing the exogamic pattern of previous generations (upper half: H, bucranium and hole), the two moieties (the long parallel stripes on the narrow side) over time send mates (chevron arms and fingers) to unite (lower half: crescent snake) and give birth (exogamic vulva) to a male (tailed animal skin) society (represented under its deathly aspect) of exogamic nature (2 parallel paws) [which will ensure its rebirth]'. It is not useless to recall that this stele is one in a dual composition. From this particular case, it can be extrapolated that every stele appears to be the timely representation of the (exogamic) subgroup of a larger entity, that is, the

endless succession of generations of one half of society when in a twin composition, or of one of its multiple sections when inserted in a sidewall. to recall that this stele is one in a dual composition. From this particular case, it can be extrapolated that every stele appears to be the timely representation of the (exogamic) subgroup of a larger entity, that is, the endless succession of generations of one half of society when in a twin composition, or of one of its multiple sections when inserted in a sidewall.

Fig. 13 Narrow side of Stele 33, Enclosure D. Göbekli Tepe III. The 'H' regenerative principle gives life to the (matrimonial network of the) society (the spider) by joining the two vertical moieties of the society at every generation (the upper – ascending – and lower – descending – sets of zigzagging snake), thus perpetuating society through time. (Drawing: aperitero CC BY-SA 4.0, from an original DAI picture: Schmidt 2007b: 109, Fig. 9).

Fig. 14 Stele 18. (Drawing: aperitro CC BY-SA 4.0, from an original DAI picture: Schmidt 2011: 81, Figs. 32-33)

Fig. 15 Multiple-legged insects between zigzagging and X-shaped snakes (approx. 15cm in width). Körtik Tepe. (Drawing from Özkaya and San 2002: 433, Fig. 3; also reproduced in Özkaya and San 2007: 23, Fig. 17-18; Schmidt 2007a: 214, Fig. 91)

This interpretation calls for further clarification. It may be surprising that society is sometimes shown under its ‘deathly aspect’. Death is not conceived as part of the life cycle; rather, death and life are equal and complementary opposites in the regeneration cycle (like males and females). This is why one necessarily implies and can stand for the other. The fact that death is represented under its exogamic nature seems to confirm the belief in reincarnation, suggested by other pictures, whereby the souls of the dead would continue, in the outer world, to respect exogamy (at least the dualist repartition of society), thereby making rebirth (new generations) possible.

21) Parallel centipedes and snakes (Fig. 15), stone bowl, Körtik Tepe (Özkaya and San 2007: 23, Fig. 18). Making the union between zigzagging snakes (exogamic lineages), multiple-legged insects seem to stand for society in time, that is, as a succession of exogamic relations in time. This union is symbolised by regularly spaced pairs of chevron-shaped legs at each generation. Looking carefully, each leg links a concave with a convex part (and *vice versa*) of the two adjacent snakes. The presence of several concentric circles “combined with wavy lines” (Benz and Bauer 2015: 4) suggests the fertility spurring out of this relation; they also sporadically appear on vessels from Qaramel, Tell ‘Abr, Hasankeyf and Gusir Höyük. However, the most explicit fertile symbol in this frieze is probably the X sign made of two geometrically crossing snakes, confirming the meaning of lineage lent to these animals. The general accent seems to be the parallel arrangement of all these elements going in the same direction and on the reciprocal nature of the relation binding them.

22) The Latmos rock paintings (Fig. 16), W. Anatolia, Late Neolithic/ Chalcolithic (Peschlow-Bindokat 2005: 57, 63, 250-251; Peschlow-Bindokat and Gerber 2012: 88-89, Figs. 13-7). These paintings feature very schematic anthropomorphic silhouettes, clearly differing by gender, with females having systematically pregnant bellies as mentioned by Peschlow-Bindocat (see above). This unrealistic feature shows that we are, here again, not in the realm of realism but in that of pure abstraction. This belly is located in the buttocks, maybe not to disturb the isomorphic balance between the two geometric figures (exogamic and equal moieties) when couples are represented. In spite of their stylistic peculiarity, several details show that these figures are connected to the general exogamic message of the Neolithic Symbolic Language (Bodet and Akdoğan 2024: 141-5). First, heads are very often made of two antithetic geometric signs, such as chevrons or ‘reversed L’, clearly portraying the idea of dualism and recalling, in the intention at least, the splayed female of Göbekli II (Pic. 13). Arms are often chevron shaped (‘exchanged

partners’). Net patterns and X signs are sometimes depicted on the pregnant abdomen of female figurines, implying a clear connection between fertility and the marital network. This belly is sometimes square, another possible reference to the fact that what is engendered by these anonymous females are not individuals but the society as a whole or a part of it (lineage/ moiety) as in the ‘basket stele’ (Pic. 31).

Fig. 16 Anthropomorphic couples, Latmos rock paintings. (from Peschlow-Bindokat 2012: 88, Fig. 13)

23) The exogamic architectural layout of Göbekli Tepe III circles. About twenty large symbolic enclosures have been identified, eight of which excavated, for the early (Late PPNA) level (III) of Göbekli Tepe (Becker *et al.* 2012: 16-18; Dietrich and Notroff 2015: 75; see the site plan by Schmidt 2011: 60, Fig. 2). In the middle of all of them stands a pair of tall isomorphic ‘twin’ monolithic steles (Fig. 17), spectacular by their size (up to 5,5 m). This disposition directly recalls the dualist scheme and the exogamic regenerative principle in purely geometric form. In this perspective, the empty central space between the twin steles can be considered as the embodiment of a vulva, the crossing of which, as we suggested, allows for the symbolic

passage from death to life and *vice versa* (Bodet 2022: 14-15). It seems to hold the same magical property as a house threshold in traditional communities, here at the level of the whole community, a ‘singularity’ reversing the inside and the outside (Bourdieu 1980), maybe somehow like the subterranean door of an igloo conceived by Canadian Inuits as a vagina into the earth matrix (Vitebsky 1995: 60-61). Thus in Göbekli Tepe, adolescents may have been asked to pass through this space during their initiation rites (McBride 2013: 59), a ceremony conceived as the symbolic death of the child and her/ his rebirth as an adult (Frazer 1910: 44). “In the scenarios of initiation, the symbolism of birth is almost always found side by side with that of death” (Eliade 1959: 191); this is still true of extant shamanistic societies. The concept of ‘Eternal return’ where time is perceived as a circular entity, seems also present here: the young person who has grown to adolescence (as a consumer) passes through this symbolic space (thence becoming a re-producer), after which, they start to turn *around* on to death.

Unlike the bull represented *below* the parturient figure or *between* the exogamic columns in Çatalhöyük (Pics 1-10), here the engendered product (the society) is represented *surrounding* the engendering principle (central twin steles). It forms a circular stone wall connecting several smaller side steles (approximately 4, 8 or 12), thereby plausibly indicating the latter's identification with the mate-exchanging subsections making up the entire tribe. Then the architectural arrangement could mean = ‘the society as a whole, made up of its subsections (inserted side steles) exchanging mates in a prearranged pattern (the surrounding wall), reproduces eternally through the action of the central exogamic regenerative

Principle (twin steles)’.

The twin steles of Göbekli Tepe are the most outstanding feature of isomorphic symbolic architectural arrangements, but they are found in every region and sub-period of Neolithic Southwest Asia (Bodet 2023). In the PPNA of the northern Levant, for example, the conception and use of communal buildings of Jerf el Ahmar, Mureybet or Tell ‘Abr were directed by a “will of symmetry” (Stordeur *et al.* 2001: 36, 41), arguably portraying the exogamic principle. The magical aura attached to these isomorphic constructions and the belief that they have a tangible impact on society's fertility would well explain why they have all been carefully buried and thus preserved upon their abandonment.

“The Exogamic Society is Stronger Than Death”

24) The ‘volcano/ leopard’ scene’ (Fig. 18), Çatalhöyük (Mellaart 1967, Shrine VII 14, Pl. 59: 133). Though there is a possibility that Hasan Dağ may be represented in this scene as Mellaart suggested, Forest (1993: 18) notes that the dots spread on it and the claws present at four extremities make it, at the same time, look like a leopard skin, that is, a symbol of physical death. Below, the tightly ordered squares may well represent the houses of Çatalhöyük as suggested by Mellaart, that is, the households and beyond, the kinship and marital structure that binds them all within a strong social unit. According to Forest, the reading of this painting can then become = ‘the matrimonial stability and collaborative structure of the entire society (neatly arranged households) successfully defies death (the leopard/ volcano) permanently wandering above’ (Forest 1993: 18).

Fig. 17 Enclosure D, with two symmetric steles standing in the middle of the stone circle wherein smaller side steles are inserted. Göbekli Tepe III. (Photo: © DAI (No. GT10_AnID_ 5807, Göbekli Tepe Project, by N. Becker, whc.unesco.org/fr/documents/165845)

Fig. 18 Shrine VII 14, the ‘volcano/ leopard’ scene (approx. 300cm in width). Çatalhöyük. (from Mellaart 1967: 133, Plate 59; image based on rendering by J. Swogger, [Flickr](https://www.flickr.com/photos/swogger/), CC BY-NC 2.0).

25) The superimposed bull-fox-crane stele (Fig. 19), Göbekli Tepe III, Enclosure A, (Schmidt 2007a: 178, Fig. 46); **26) the hunter-killing bull** (Fig. 20), left half of the Sayburç relief (Özdoğan E. 2022, Fig. 4); **27) the ‘deer-hunt’** (Fig. 21) and **28) ‘bull-hunt’ paintings**, Çatalhöyük (Mellaart 1967: 98, Fig. 54, 134-6, Fig. 61-4, 171, Fig. 48; Hodder 2007, vol. 2: 313, Fig. 18). These four scenes seem to bear the same message. The bull and the deer (the society) are above mortuary elements, either physical death (hunters and carnivorous animals) or spiritual afterlife (cranes). They are generally proportionally bigger than the latter and/ or placed in a central or dominant position compared to them. The bucrania are out of proportion in all four pictures, depicted frontally to render the two horns visible. Only one should be visible since heads are in profile; as we saw, this technique is probably here to emphasise the exogamic relation between the two moieties. All four compositions can thus be read as ‘the society as a whole (the bull/ deer) respecting exogamy (the two horns/ antlers) is stronger than the death permanently surrounding, confronting and taking away its individuals’. Beyond the message, the uniformity in pictographic techniques and symbols spanning at least 3000 years and several hundred kilometres (in fact, most of Neolithic Southwest Asia) makes it possible to talk about a symbolic *koiné* based upon a universally shared message, exogamy.

29) The snake net (Fig. 22), Stele 1, Enclosure A, Göbekli Tepe III (Schmidt 2007b: 113, Fig. 20) appears as the image of the matrimonial template according to which each lineage (each snake) systematically exchanges its mates (points of junction between snakes = pre-arranged marriages) at every generation. This inalterable and endless (a head terminates snakes at each end) matrimonial net pattern makes up the strength and stability of the entire society

through time and space and recalls directly the village houses pictured in the ‘volcano/ leopard scene’, Çatalhöyük (Pic. 24). The net thus shows the exogamic lineages in their diachrony (through time, from one head to its opposite) and in their synchrony (the points of junction).

Fig 19 Stele 2, Enclosure A (approx. 90cm in width). Göbekli Tepe III. (Photo: “Reliefs of animals, Göbekli Tepe III, c. 9000 BCE” by Klaus-Peter Simon, licenced under CC BY-SA 3.0)

Fig. 20 The Sayburç relief (left part; approx. 80cm in height). (from Özdoğan E. 2022, Fig. 4; Photo: B. Köşker)

Fig. 21 The 'bull-hunt' paintings (bull approx. 135cm in height). Çatalhöyük. (from Mellaart 1967: 136, Fig. 64; drawing: © O. Hoftun, CC BY-SA 3.0)

Interestingly, nine snakeheads are at the bottom and eight at the top. In this matrimonial system indeed, termed 'generalised' by Lévi-Strauss (1967), every lineage gives a mate to the next (A to B, B to C,

etc.), and the last lineage gives its mate back to the first (H to A) to close the circle, thence delineating the extent of the whole tribe and its endogamous matrimonial network (Bodet 2012). One of the op-

posed heads of the last lineage is then represented twice, the second giving a mate arguably to be received by the first snake on the opposite side to close the circle. If this decipherment is correct, it would be a very ingenious way to represent the closed matrimonial exchange circle on a flat surface. This interpretation could find some support in the fact that enclosure A, to which this stele belongs, has four parallel steles, thus possibly making up eight exogamic moieties, but this hypothesis will remain speculative as this enclosure, intermediary in date between Göbekli Tepe III and II, has a different (rectangular) layout. This pictorial technique may also explain why one of the 12 snakeheads is lacking on one of the two edges of the narrow side of Stele 33 (Pic. 19, *supra*).

Fig. 22 The snake net Stele 1, Enclosure A. Göbekli Tepe III. (Drawing: aperitero CC BY-SA 4.0, from an original DAI picture: Schmidt 2007a: 177, Fig. 45; see also 2007b: 113, Fig. 20)

30) 'Birds caught in the net' (Fig. 23), Stele 12, *etc.* C, Göbekli Tepe III (Schmidt 2007a 188: Fig. 59; 2007b: 108, Fig. 7). This net (without snakes but probably with a similar matrimonial connotation) is on the head part of a side stele. In the background, five birds flying in the same direction are depicted, seemingly trapped in the net. They could represent the souls of dead individuals, unable to tear apart the solid matrimonial fabric of the society. These birds could imply a belief in reincarnation, where the matrimonial network of the society would re-collect its souls. Indeed, among

“central and northern tribes (of Australia), all human beings descend, by perpetual reincarnation, from the primal totemic beings” (Lang 1905: 319), and among the native communities of Borneo, ancestors (notably the founders of the community) are ‘transformed’ in ‘spirits’ sometimes involved in the process of rebirth and reincarnation (Couderc and Sillander 2012: 3, 23). The idea that these birds could be the souls of dead individuals is partly reinforced by the carnivorous animals baring teeth (wild boar and fox) placed just beneath, on the body part of the stele (invisible in Fig. 23). The souls on top could then be those delivered by physical death represented below, a disposition also known from Pic. 39. The hypothetical meaning of the whole may then be something along the lines of ‘the compact matrimonial structure (the net) traps the souls (birds) of dead individuals (boar, fox) [for the newborns to reuse?].’

Fig. 23 Birds caught in the net, Stele 12, Enclosure C (approx. 130cm in width at top). The souls flying (cranes?) from dead bodies (teethed boar/ fox) and retained by the matrimonial network. Göbekli Tepe III. (Photo by Klaus-Peter Simon, with CC BY-SA 3.0 license, original file: [Göbekli2012-3.jpg](#); see also Schmidt 2007a 188: Fig. 59; 2007b: 108, Fig. 7)

31) The 'basket stele' (Fig. 24), Stele 43, Enclosure D, Göbekli Tepe III (Schmidt 2011: 78, Fig. 29): on the top (head) part of this crowded and confusing stele, the eye is caught by three big rectangles (the tribe/ clan?) represented with their upper corners connected by a semi-circular ‘handle’, making them look like baskets. Given what is now known of Neolithic symbolism, the handle could suggest a dualistic sign, plausibly connecting the two moieties (squares) of which every rectangle is virtually composed (so 6 moieties in all). This interpretation remains putative as the separation between the moieties is not represented (or in a very shallow way for the two side rectangles?). Still, the emphasis seems to be put here on the strength of each of the three represented rectangles/ societies, an impression undermined should the halves (suggested by the handle anyway) be clearly depicted (but see the following paragraph). These big rectangles stand over a *kilim-*

like background made of a regular pattern of chevrons spurring alternately inward and outward from a central line of small squares following each other endlessly, a frieze likely to represent the exogamic society through time. These small squares could represent halves, that is, moieties, of a larger unity (the tribe) like the big rectangles above. Some details support this. Looking closely at this kilim pattern, outward chevrons usually bind one square to the next. In contrast, inward chevrons regularly fall in the space between two squares, as if the children of one generation became the sexual mates of (the adverse moiety of) the following generation. This would represent a faithful pictorial depiction of how ‘primitive communist’ societies, as analysed by Testart (1985), conceive their perpetuation in time, generation after generation.

Fig. 24 ‘Basket’ Stele (Pillar 43), Enclosure D (approx. 150cm in width at top). Göbekli Tepe III. The rectangles are possible pictograms for the society as a whole, and the ‘handle’ on top for the exogamic relation between its halves. (Photo: © DAI, Göbekli Tepe Project. whc.unesco.org/en/documents/165846; see also Schmidt 2011: 78, Fig. 29)

The three big rectangles on top could then be the exogamic (handle) moieties of the overall society, appearing as a momentary close-up extracted from an endless succession of exogamic generations succeeding one another in time (small squares in the background frieze). The number three remains puzzling (the relation between the 2nd and the 3rd squares topped by an animal's handle-shaped horn needs to be clarified). It may have no specific meaning, but it may also be that, as in Pics. 14, 18, 29 and 36, each of the two side rectangles would be reduplicated as one of the two halves making up the central rectangle, as if to represent the society's exogamic engendering principle itself, but this, again, must remain a speculation. In case the ‘handle’ indeed happened to join two moieties, then, in the symbolic repertoire, as suggested by other authors (*supra*), quadrilateral shapes could stand for the ‘society’ as a whole or as a part (like the houses of the volcano scene, Pic. 24, or the diamonds in the snake net, Pic. 29). It

would also highlight the pictorial ingenuity, with the ‘snapshot’ technic already encountered on the narrow side of Stele 33 (Pic. 19).

Furthermore, in the upper part of the stele, a big vulture's head (death), with parallel wings made of unnaturally symmetrical feathers and legs, appears spurring out from the kilim background. It is depicted at the same close-up level as the big rectangles, along with a circle (full moon?) and two small cranes *below* the big rectangles. The general disposition could show that death, always around and inevitable, remains nevertheless below, that is, under the ‘control’ of the regenerative power of the exogamic society.

Below, on the ‘body’ part of the stele, there is a vast scorpion right in the centre with its phallic tail and symmetrical chevron-shaped legs on either side (exogamic) pointing towards a snake (the lineage: life symbol) placed above several deathly signs: a toothed carnivorous animal, a giant crane's head and a headless ithyphallic man. This composition is elusive, but the beneficent signs (scorpion, snake) also seem to dominate and be more central than the maleficent ones (crane, carnivorous teeth, headless/ soul-less man). If there is a unity to the whole stele, then, hypothetically, the exogamic scorpion at the bottom could stand as the ‘earthly’ male regenerative principle and product (the society) of an endless ‘heavenly’ (*i.e.*, mythical, conceptual) matrimonial process on the top part of the stele.

“The Engendering Principle Under its Deleterious Aspect”

32 - 33) Stone sculptures of *antithetic figures topped with a big bird*. Better preserved, the double-headed limestone composition from Nevalı Çori (Fig. 25, left - Hauptmann 2007: 126, Fig. 14a-b) combines all elements of the exogamic message. Two female faces look in opposite directions, probably standing for the two separated and exogamic moieties but related to one another by the net pattern of their merged hair, possibly standing for the marital network binding them (and in particular for its fertile function as the small hole in the middle could imply). Below, the two arms cross in a conspicuous X sign; the fingers depicted at their tips possibly indicate, here again, the individual mates exchanged by each moiety. The arms go downwards and seem to be placed, at least according to Schmidt's reconstitution, above a hollow circle at loin level. If there is indeed such a hole, it would represent a single vulva shared by the two female figures, standing for a threshold to life, that is, to the perpetual regeneration of the society as a whole. Finally, the two exogamic heads are topped by a unique and majestic bird, a probable symbol of death, standing for the ascending generations swallowed by the regenerative principle (X sign). We note that con-

a

b

Fig. 25 Free-standing sculpted compositions with twin female faces topped with a bird, from Nevalı Cori (*left*; approx. 100cm in height) and Göbekli Tepe (*right*; approx. 192cm in height). *left*: drwg. reconstituted by apitero CC BY-SA 4.0 from an original drawing and photos by Schmidt 2010: 247-8, Figs. 16-8); *right*: photo from “Urfa Museum Totem sept 2019 4806” by Dosseman, licenced under CC BY-SA 4.0

trary to the heads and arms, the bird and the vulva are not only unique but are placed at both vertical ends of the remaining composition, plausibly standing for the complementary opposition of life and death, separated by the exogamic union of the two moieties. But as a reviewer mentioned, the statue is not complete so it is difficult to talk in finite terms.

Below the hollow/ vulva, we see, according to the reconstitution by Schmidt (2010: 248, Fig. 17), two birds looking at each other, their beaks touching each other. It is difficult to know how loyal to the original the reconstitution of this lower part is and how these lower birds are related to the rest of the sculpture, but the total would make sense. 'Recycling souls (?) of the ascending generations (the bird above/death), two mutually exclusive moieties (looking in opposed directions) keep on sending each other mates (the crossed arms/ X sign) through a pre-defined and fertile matrimonial network (the net of the two hairs merging around a hole). Their intercourse eternally gives life through the vulva below to two new and complementary lineages represented under their deathly aspect (the two converging lower birds)'. In the case of a belief in reincarnation, the two lower birds could, here again, signify that exogamy prevails even in the otherworld. In this dimension, where moieties look at each other 'in the eyes', contrary to the antithetic faces of the living society above, and may even exchange mates (parallel toes), their differentiation (Girard 1972) does not seem to be threatened by uniformity, that is, by endogamous intercourse.

The Göbekli Tepe statue (Fig. 25, right - Schmidt 2010: 239) is poorly preserved. Still, below what appears to be the fingers of the two arms (union of the moieties), we see a smaller figure, apparently human (a child, standing for a descending generation?), coming down with his own two hands and fingers likewise turned downward and towards each other as if about to reproduce the same exogamic union in the next generation. In both sculptures, we thus seem to have the same society at different stages in time (ascending, interacting and descending) but represented at once, according to the same exogamic pattern/ principle. With different attributes and prerogatives befitting their place in time, these various stages of society are shown to be intrinsically linked to each other on a diachronic level. It is tempting to draw a parallel with Stele 33 (Pic. 19), where the two moieties interact (H) so that the ascending generation (the upper set of three snakes) continues as a new generation (the three descending snakes). The link between past, present and future generations, embodying the Eternal return and maybe reincarnation, appears quite common.

34) The 'vulture scene', wall painting, Çatalhöyük - VII.21 and VII.B.8 (Mellaart 1967: 169, Fig. 47):
Neo-Lithics 23

death is represented with vultures eating the flesh of beheaded humans, illustrating the carnivorous and psychopomp characteristics of these birds (Tresidder 2000: 70-2; 2003: 299; Benz and Bauer 2015: 5-9), that is, the omnipresence of death always lingering above the society (Forest 1993: 17). The two wings are large, each made of about 8 to 12 parallel long feathers (and a few smaller ones – filiation?) joined at the top. They possibly refer to the mate-exchanging lineages of each of the two moieties of the Çatalhöyük community. The two-moiety system becomes in time an abstraction, conceived as such, even when the actual kinship system of the community becomes divided under demographic pressure into 8 or 12 (still exogamic) sections, a situation well documented in many Aborigines tribes from Australia (Frazer 1910: 106-10). On (or in?) the bird bellies, parallel lines are also depicted as if to represent the perpetuation of this exogamic organisation in the netherworld. Also, as seen in the left part, the two superposed 'eaten' individuals are splayed between two converging vultures, as if the two moieties were represented under their deathly aspect. The link drawn between exogamic moieties on the one hand and ascending (dead)/ descending (future) generations on the other also seems to appear through the vultures' location on the northern and eastern walls (Fig. 3), cardinal points respectively attached to these two concepts. Deathly symbolism is thus a habitual component of the daily life of society (Bourdieu 1980).

35) The female statuette with leopard shoulders (Mellaart 1967: 182, Fig. 49) supports the idea that limbs in general (elsewhere prolonged by the armrests: Pic. 12) represent the two mate-exchanging lineages of the moieties, here seen through their deathly aspect, as an intrinsic part of the regenerative whole.

36) The ithyphallic man between converging lions (Fig. 26), Sayburç relief – right-hand half (Özdoğan E. 2022: Fig. 5): the general dualistic composition is evident from the two antithetic teeth-showing felines (deadly elements), probably standing for the two mate-exchanging moieties. The marital connotation, in particular, is supported by the fact that only one of the felines has a phallus and that on the man's chest, a double chevron goes (downward) from one shoulder/arm to the other (they even seem to join the muzzles and teeth of the two side lions). As often, arms and hands probably stand for the exogamic lineages. The fingers of one hand are drawn (exchanged mates?) while the other is holding the penis, a possible association between exogamy and fertility.

Despite the conceptual similarity with other symbolic depictions, this composition is unique in that the two lions converge towards a male anthropomorphic figure. Besides the latter's central position, its prominence is shown by its depiction in high relief while the two felines are incised. This

central position is generally reserved for the female regenerating principle, but, as seen elsewhere (the spider on the narrow side of Stele 33, Pic. 19; the scorpion in the ‘basket stele’, Pic. 31), the feminine principle can be represented through the traits of its male product. More importantly, this figure is generally said to be human, but the face looks much more like that of a feline, with its pointed ears and protruding muzzle. Its outline, in particular, recalls the head of the parturient reliefs on Çatalhöyük wall plasters (Pics. 1-2, 6). This depiction lends much weight to the idea that the head of the figure must be that of a carnivorous animal (eliminating ascending generations), making sense, by the same token, of the systematic and ritual destruction of the head in Çatalhöyük (though, interestingly, not here).

This scene may be roughly read as follows = ‘the central fertile male society, generated by the interaction of exogamic moieties (under their deadly aspect: side felines of both sexes), devouring ascending generations (feline head of the central figure), is its own regenerative principle’.

Fig. 26 The Sayburç relief, right part. (from E. Özdoğan 2022, Fig. 5; photo: K. Akdemir) <https://doi.org/10.15184/aqy.2022.125>)

Appending note: Some readers may feel lost at this point, the regenerative principle being now male and deathly. Yet, we have seen that, even when feminine, this principle is also very often represented under its deathly aspect. As for the male appearance, even if as a rule a female symbol represents the regenerative principle, Gimbutas notes (1989: 64) that some symbols are often interchangeable. The regenerative symbol thus sometimes may take a masculine aspect, following the rule that the ‘principle’ can replace its ‘product’ and *vice versa*.

37) The two vulture steles, Jerf el Ahmar (Helmer *et al.* 2004: 150, Fig. 2B): two 90 cm tall vulture-shaped steles frame the stone slab bench (where two headless anthropomorphic schematic figures are incised) running along the wall of a circular communal building. Seating on these slabs, a council of elders could well have been entitled to ensure the perpetuation of ancient

(exogamic) traditions and events concerning the community (communal decisions, initiation rites, *etc.*). Like the niche in the *Kultgebäude* of Nevalı Çori, the place in the bench delineated by the two vulture steles is likely to have been reserved for one or two specific person(s) within this council, possibly the closer living descendants (on a unilineal descent line) to the founding ancestor(s) of the tribe (Forest 1996a: 24). The genealogical link between elders and remembered ancestors, especially those deemed to be the ‘founders’ of the community, is indeed known to still play an essential role in the extant societies of Kalimantan (Borneo) for example (Couderc and Sillander 2012: 15, 45-46). Somebody sitting there would recall the ‘mistress of animals’ statuette from Çatalhöyük (Pic. 12), except that the two leopards are here replaced by psychopomp vultures (Gourichon 2002: 149; Helmer *et al.* 2004: 158) conceivably standing for the souls of ascending generations. There is no need, however, in such societies, where everyone is related, to think in terms of social hierarchy. Every *communal* matter is probably dealt with *communally* in the interest of the *community on the whole* (Barnard 2020: 30-1, 47), but for practical reasons, especially once the population has grown under the double effect of sedentism and regular supply of increasing farmed food, decision making has to be handed down to a reduced number of persons.

38) Panthers joining their paws, incised limestone slabs, Tell ‘Abr (Yartah 2004: 150, Figs 11-12). On two adjoining stone slabs of a communal building there are, two on one slab and three on the other, identical panthers, incised symmetrically side by side with their paws (and even their ears) stretched out towards each other, unnaturally and geometrically. The relationship between the panthers is so intimate that they share the same claws. The two-panthers picture is likely to represent two exogamic moieties (represented under their deathly aspect). However, the three-panther composition, making an XXX pattern like the tortoise composition from Nevalı Çori (Pic. 14), is unlikely to stand for three exogamic lineages involved in a generalised mating pattern as nothing indicates that the two at the extremities join each other. Like the three parallel snakes from Stele 33 (Pic. 19) or the three squares from the ‘basket stele’ (Pic. 31), this arrangement possibly reduplicates (half of?) each of the side moieties in the middle panther to represent the unique product of their union, that is, the exogamic regenerative society, represented here under its deathly aspect (panther).

39) The twin cranes over the pair of onagers, Çatalhöyük: this interesting quote by Russell and McGowan (2003: 448-449, Fig. 5) befits the views presented here: “in a little-known painting (...) at Çatalhöyük, two cranes face each other with raised heads (Mellaart 1966: 190, Plates LXII-LXIII; see

Figure 5). (...) The facing pair of animals is a repeated theme in Çatalhöyük art (and elsewhere, *e.g.*, Welté 1989) and, for example, is seen in a pair of onagers immediately below these cranes as well as the facing leopard reliefs. The cranes may thus be linked into a larger symbolic system of pairs or twins". Like the birds caught in the net (Pic. 30), interpreted as the souls delivered by the physical death represented in the carnivorous animals below, the two cranes above the two onagers here may represent the souls of the two moieties themselves. And like the converging birds at the bottom of the double-faced statue of Nevalı Çori (Pic. 32), this could be another hint at a belief in reincarnation, in which the exogamic arrangement would follow the 'eternally returning' souls even in the afterworld.

Fig. 27 Splayed clawed animal, incised stone (approx. 8cm in width at bottom). Tell Qaramel. (from Mazurowski 2003: 369, Fig. 12; with kind permission of R. Mazurowski)

40) The two antithetic leopards, Leopard Shrine (Fig. 3, VI.44), Çatalhöyük (Mellaart 1967: 43-44, Figs. 18-21), would represent the unity of the society divided between its two convergent and complementary moieties represented under their 'deathly' and male aspect, the raised symmetric tails being possibly phallic symbols.

41) Pairs of human skulls, Skull Building, MPPNB Çayönü (Özbek 2004: 18-22): among many exogamic features appearing in the symbolic architecture of this site (Bodet 2023: 103-104), several skulls of men and women have been deposited antagonistically, one looking to the east, the other to the west, arguably expanding the exogamic principle in the other world. This disposition, according to the cardinal points, whereby every day the sun is 'born' and 'dies' before 'resurrecting' the following day, is essential and must be interpreted as a symbol in itself (Bourdieu 1980), just like the organisation of the decorations in Çatalhöyük houses (Forest 1993: 15).

42) The splayed reptile (Fig. 27). On a stone shaft straightener from Tell Qaramel (Mazurowski 2003: 369, Fig. 12), a reptile or feline (?) touches two sets of

parallel lines (those at the extremities being zigzagging) with its stretched limbs and claws. The exogamic principle is also a deathly symbol (swallowing ascending generations?), while the sidelines give a sense of eternity to this regenerative process.

Fig. 28 Parturient reliefs with limbs turned upwards, 'Shrine' VII.23 (approx. 60 cm in height and width). Çatalhöyük H (from Mellaart 1967: 76, Plate VII; with permission by A. Mellaart)

The following citations are reproduced to show that the mingling of deathly and dualistic elements is more common in the Neolithic symbolism than the few cases reviewed here: **43)** in Bouqras, an 80cm long frieze features "15 painted [birds] and two scratched into the plaster. Two more painted birds were found (...) in the same room" (Clason 1989/90: 209, Footnote 2) - these birds have been identified as cranes and ostriches, all facing to the left; **44)** at Göbekli Tepe, "the sides (of the central steles) facing each other sometimes bear the same species, for example, a fox in enclosure B" (Peters *et al.* 2005: 231-232).

Single Representations

The knowledgeable viewer, now trained to 'read' the connection between elements in compositions, can easily recognise them in single elements and make sense of them despite their isolation. Only a few characteristic examples will be briefly described as the primary overall 'reading' is everywhere homogenous.

45) Parturient reliefs with limbs turned upwards (Fig. 28), Çatalhöyük, 'Shrines' VI.A.50, VII.23, VII.1, VI.A.8, VI.B.8 and VII.31 (Fig. 3) (Mellaart 1967: 103-4, 155: Figs. 45, 76: pl. VII). The part of the limbs unnaturally bent in a vertical position seems to stand in place of the two columns (standing for the exogamic moieties but not represented here), typically surrounding or supporting the parturient figure, thus providing a sense of time (generation after generation). The fertile characteristic of the exogamic arrangement is emphasised here by the concentric circles on the navel (Mellaart 1967; Forest 1993: 4, Fig. 1).

46) The 'Bear stamp', Çatalhöyük (Fig. 29), (Hodder 2007, Vol.2: 316, Fig. 20; 2012: 275, Fig. 19): the same upward turned limbs are found in an animal 'stamp' from the same site. The head is shaped like a carnivorous animal (a bear?). Exogamy and physical death are here clearly depicted as constitutive of the same element. This piece gives some weight to the idea that the systematically erased/ broken head of the parturient figure modelled on Çatalhöyük walls may have been that of a carnivorous animal ('devouring' past generations).

Fig. 29 Splayed bear stamp seal. (approx. 9.5cm in width). Çatalhöyük. (from Hodder 2007, vol.2: 316, Fig. 20)

47) Single felines or boars with splayed limbs (Fig. 30) are also known from Göbekli Tepe (Schmidt 2007a: 164-5, Figs. 25-26, 184, Fig. 54⁷). The splayed limbs are always represented with upward-turned tips like the female picture above, and sometimes with claws expressly detailed: such unnatural and emphasized details certainly have a meaning, arguably related, again, to the exogamic principle under its male (phallic tail) and maleficent aspect (death).

48) Teeth-baring carnivorous animals (Fig. 31) are common in Göbekli Tepe (Hauptmann 1999, vol. 2: 50, Fig. 20; 53, Figs. 29-31). The two rows of teeth are highly prominent compared to the rest of the head, undoubtedly because they are an ideogram, arguably standing for swallowing and destroying, that is, for physical death.

49-50) The male felines in the Lion-Pillar Building in Göbekli Tepe II (Schmidt 2007a: 289, Fig. 102) and on Pillar 1 in Göbekli Tepe III (Hauptmann 1999: 51, 24). Conspicuously baring their teeth, they are both represented with equally unnatural, perfectly parallel and isomorphic paws (while, represented in profile, only should be visible), all ending with noticeably detailed claws. Exogamy, fertility, and death are again assembled in the same entity.

Fig. 30 Splayed animal sculpture with claws (approx. 47cm in width). Göbekli Tepe III. ("Urfa museum Animal relief sept 2019 4772.jpg" by Dosseman, with CC BY-SA 4.0 license)

Fig. 31 Outstandingly teeth-baring feline (approx. 32 cm in length). ("Urfa museum Animal statuette sept 2019 4754" by Dosseman, licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0)

51) The still-standing male statue (Fig. 32) from Urfa (Schmidt 2010: 246, Fig. 14): the arms and hands represent the exogamic lineages, and the idea of partners reciprocally exchanged is explicit with every

Fig. 32 Standing male (approx. 180cm in height), unearthed below the old city of Urfa. ("Urfa museum – Urfa Man, sept 2019 4881" by Dosseman, licenced under CCBY-SA 4.0)

finger placed in front of the corresponding finger of the opposite hand (like on the narrow side of the huge Stele 18; Pic. 20). The fingers about to join are located just above the penis, an arrangement plausibly to be related to the fertility and the regenerative power of the exogamic relation. The two parallel triangular chevrons on the chest, starting from the shoulders and

pointing downward (like in Sayburç, Pic. 36), may reduplicate the same meaning as an eternal, active symbol for the society as a whole (past-present-future). The statue contains a dualistic 'sparkling' detail rarely found elsewhere: the two eye-sockets are filled with black obsidian (Schmidt 2010: 247). A parallel is known from Yiftahel, where the eye-sockets of three plastered skulls are filled with shells (Schechter *et al.* 2021: 1).

52) Isomorphic hands and fingers, narrow side of the stele from the *Löwenpfeilerggebäude*, Göbekli Tepe II (Schmidt 2007a: 288, Fig. 101; 2007b: 110, Fig. 11). Contrary to the roughly executed fingers of the previous statue, here, the isomorphic outlook of the fingers of both hands is rendered with geometric precision, as it was on the twin stele 18 (Pic. 20). The fingers are placed just below a rectangular sign open on top: recalling the square niche in Pic. 11, Çatalhöyük, the latter could represent a mouth (death), but because it seems to be placed around the loin, a symbolic womb is also possible; both interpretations are, in fact, absolutely conceivable at the same time (*vagina dentata*). In any case, even if the enclosed exact meaning and mythical details will always escape us, at a structural level, nothing is random: the connection between reciprocal matrimonial alliance and regeneration (whether under its death-giving or its life-giving aspect or both at the same time) is structuring the picture.

53) Stone head with a snake, Nevalı Çori Kultgebäude (Hauptmann 1999: 44, Fig. 10). "Carefully placed to be visible between the two pillars" (McBride 2013: 53) upon entering the building, this head has a curving snake carved on its back. The snake plausibly refers to the society alternatively receiving and sending mates from and to its two (suggested) moieties. These two moieties could also be incarnated by the other visible feature in this sculpture, the two protruding ears (?)

54) A phalломorphic female (breasts visible) figurine, Çatalhöyük⁸: the "ambiguity, both in terms of form and sex" (Meskell and Nakamura 2005, Fig. 80) confirms once more that concepts, and not people, are represented: the regenerating feminine principle may here be shown mingled together with her product, the male society.

55) The Tırşin Yaylası figures, Eastern Taurus (Özdoğan M. 2007a: 439, Fig. 7-8) show schematic representations of wild goats and bison in profile but with their two disproportionate parallel horns visible, while only one should naturally appear, a common technique (Pics. 23-6) emphasizing the exogamic principle.

The following examples display replicated representations but incorporate our 'single representation' class because their duality is represented under a unique anthropomorphic form (standing for a single entity, the society as a whole).

56) The double-headed human statuettes⁹, facing in the same direction and unified in the same body, found in a cache at Ain Ghazal (Rollefson 2002: 174, Fig. 7; Aurenche and Kozłowski 1999: 153) are quite possibly another expression of the dualism intrinsically composing the society.

57) The ‘double goddess’ in one body, Çatalhöyük, with “two heads, two pairs of breasts, but a single pair of arms” (Mellaart 1967: 141, caption Fig. 70-72), appears as a figurative symbol of the exogamic exchange binding together the two moieties for the perpetuation of the dualistic but intrinsically unified society.

58) A beheaded female figurine, Shrine VI.A.61, Çatalhöyük (Mellaart 1967: 182, Fig. 50), displays symmetric pairs of large Greek crosses painted over her body, one on each shoulder, elbow, leg and breast, confirming once more the connection between this geometric sign, the symmetrical body parts and the fertility principle.

Geometric and Schematic Representations

Certain geometric signs have been interpreted as synthesising figurative depictions (+, H or X standing for the regenerative principle, O for the womb, > for the marital mates *etc.*). In contrast, specific anthropomorphic or zoomorphic figures are displayed in exaggeratedly geometric postures (the snake net, the tortoise, leopards, human as XXX, *etc.*). Always organised with a strong sense of symmetry, these patterns appear (to the initiated) as comprehensive, simple and straightforward representations of the exogamic message. A few others ought now to be added to the list to support the idea that they bear a definite and predefined meaning.

59) *Linear and geometric motifs* (Mellaart 1967: 85-93, Figs. 29-45) painted on walls, Çatalhöyük: numerous parallel straight lines probably represent the two moieties as clearly distinct entities, and the zigzagging or meandering lines represent them reciprocally sending mates to each other (a recurrent motif in the iconography of classical times, the famous Greek meander motif is undoubtedly a revival of this prehistoric pattern). As noted above, chevrons and triangles are the isolated tips of these zigzags, thus standing for the mates moving from one lineage to the other. In some instances, a circular shape (the regenerative principle) comprises four triangles (married male mates) or triangular voids waiting to be ‘filled’ by the triangles ‘floating’ around (male mates waiting to be married) to keep the regenerative process of the society going on (Forest 1993: 28-30).

60) *The ‘kilim pattern’* (Fig. 33) has been identified among Çatalhöyük wall paintings by Mellaart (1967: 85-9, Figs. 29-40, 155, Fig. 45). Described as a succession of diamonds or crosses, Forest (1993: 21-

28) convincingly showed that they represented the endless succession of exogamic generations following one another (on the vertical axis), the ascending ones being ‘devoured’ (dying) and the descending ones being delivered (born), through a regenerative process systematically fuelled by the exogamic union of mates coming from two moieties (on the horizontal axis). It is probably not these rhythmic decorations that look like kilims but actual kilims that have perpetuated a stylistic tradition going back at least to the Neolithic.

61) *‘Sun pattern’* (Fig. 34) incised on Körtik Tepe bowls (Arbuckle and Özkaya 2006: 115, Fig. 2; Özkaya and San 2007: 22, Figs. 15-6) and **62)** at least on one from Tell Qaramel (Mithen *et al.* 2023: 836, Fig. 4c, redrawn from Mazurowski 2003). Large and regularly spaced ‘X’ signs are depicted on the surface of these stone bowls. The central points of intersection are surrounded by large concentric circles (fertile nature of the interaction between moieties) connected by two symmetric horizontal bands (probably to express the idea of reciprocal exchange). This geometric decoration suggests that the regenerative process of lineages complement each other in the (restricted and circular) reciprocal matrimonial network of the society as a whole (closed and turned on itself: the surface of the bowl).

63) *Another ‘sun’ pattern* is incised on the stone slab of a communal building at Tell ‘Abr (Yartah 2004: 152, Fig. 14). Its branches (made of two parallel bands) equally intersect in a circle (fertile centre), but, here, the tips of the branches are connected to each other by two horizontal zigzagging lines below and above (the two exchanging moieties), in a purely dualistic composition.

64) *The megalithic ‘porthole’*, Göbekli Tepe III (Schmidt 2011: 79, Fig. 30). This big stone slab is pierced by two large window-like rectangular openings, side by side, possibly standing for two moieties, separated (or joined) by a narrow and vertical jamb (the society in time?). This disposition clearly, recalls the geometric wall modeling from Çatalhöyük in Pic. 10 (Fig 6). The symbolic and exogamic nature of this piece is emphasised by three animals (reptiles?) depicted in a characteristic splayed (XXX) position just below the openings and by a series of 7 or 8 small round depressions on each side, plausibly representing the exchanging lineages of the two moieties.

65) *In the Eastern Taurus, isolated geometric patterns* and schematic anthropo- or zoomorphic figures following an isomorphic pattern and certainly related to exogamic lineages go back at least to the Epipalaeolithic/ Neolithic transition, as in Hallan Çemi (Rosenberg 2011: 75, Fig. 12), Boncuklu Tarla (Kodaş *et al.* 2022: 7, Fig. 8), Körtik Tepe (Özkaya and Coşkun 2013: 34-39) and Hasankeyf Höyük (Miyake 2013: 45, Fig. 1).

Fig. 33 The 'kilim pattern', Shrine VIA50 and VIB 1. Çatalhöyük. The vertical succession of 'X' signs (1) stands for the perpetual regenerative principle, 'swallowing' ascendant generations by the mouth ('bouche') and engendering descendant ones by the vagina (4), through the exchange of exogamic mates between the two parallel moieties/ lineages (vertical lines) composing the society as a whole (1-3). The four converging triangles give the complete ternary diagram, while the binary diagram (zigzags) reduces the latter to the succession of exogamic generations in time. The black diamond inserted between crosses, understood as two superimposed sets of two opposed triangles, recalls the cycle of life and death, whereby an engendered generation (the top point) expands until it makes the junction between the opposite moieties at puberty (the two side points) and invariably fades (narrows down) until its inevitable death (bottom end). (From Forest 1993: 20, Fig. 6)

66) In the earliest Neolithic of the Northern Levant, isolated symmetric symbols are likewise very common. Schematic vultures, beaked crosses, X signs, symmetric straight and zigzagging lines, repeated chevrons with dots, diamonds, meanders, Greek or hatched crosses and net or grid patterns are commonly known from engraved pebbles and shaft straighteners probably related to the exogamic principle. Such examples are found at Tell 'Abr, Jerf el Ahmar, Neo-Lithics 23

Mureybet, Cheikh Hassan, Dja'de or Bouqras (Cauvin 1997: 71-2, Figs. 19-20, 243, Fig. 63; Stordeur 2003: 24-5 Figs. 1, 2, 4; Coqueugniot 2011: 155, Figs. 4-7, 10; Benz and Bauer 2015: 11-12, Figs. 8b-9).

67) Similar geometric patterns are also common in the Southern Levant, at Jilat, Netiv Hagdud, Munhata, and Aswad, among others, and in the piedmont of the Zagros as at Ali Kosh (Cauvin 1997: 71-2, Figs. 19-20; Aurenche and Kozłowski 1999: 214, 219-20, pl. 2-12, 213; Rosenberg 2011: 75, Fig. 9).

68) Late Neolithic geometric signs (crosses, parallel lines, etc.) perpetuate the dualist symbolism in much later periods (Final Neolithic and Chalcolithic) throughout Mesopotamia, especially on the painted domestic pottery of Halaf, Hassuna, Samarra and Ubaid periods. The dualist principle was still obviously vivid, though gradually fading away (Forest 1996b: 36-9, Figs 21-8).

Fig. 34 'Sun pattern', stone bowl, Körtek Tepe (from Arbuckle and Özkaya 2006: 115, Fig. 2). The central concentric circles at the center of each X seems to stand for the fertility stemming from the intersection of the moieties.

The following list is a quick inventory of such late Neolithic geometric signs found in different Anatolian regions where geometric motifs appear as painted, modelled or incised on ceramic or stone vessels. 69) the Tigris basin, at Hakemi Use (Tekin 2011: 165-9, Fig. 4-9) or Salat Cami Yanı (Miyake 2011: 147, Figs. 17-20); 70) the Euphrates basin at Mezraa-Teleilat (Özdoğan 2007b: 193-4, Figs. 61-62) and in the Çukurova at Mersin (Caneva 2007, Figs. 28-29); 71) Central Anatolia, at late aceramic Neolithic Aşıklı Höyük, Cappadocia (Esin and Hamankaya 2007: 272, Fig. 25), the Konya area and in the ceramic Neolithic of the Lake region, like in Hacılar and Höyücek (Duru 2007: 321, Figs. 8, 25, 37).

72) Some vases from Köşk Höyük are worth a specific mention (Öztan 2007: 220-227, Figs. 13-25): on one of them, two prominent antlers (probably the two alternatively mate-exchanging lineages), painted white on dark, spur out of a comparatively small deer head. A schematic female figure in an isomorphic position, with chevron-shaped arms, fingers and

breasts (fertility deriving from the exogamic exchange?), is visible on another one. Still, another vase features two very schematic females joined by their adjacent arms, one extending her other arm towards a child (fertility and filiation stemming from a reciprocal matrimonial exchange between matrilineal moieties?). Animals in reliefs with unnatural depictions of both horns are also known from Tepecik Çiftlik vessels (Bıçakçı *et al.* 2007: 249-252, Figs. 35-41).

73) *The Aegean region* features several schematic dualistic signs. Noteworthy is an anthropomorphic vessel from Ulucak (Çilingiroğlu A. and Ç. 2007: 348, Fig. 8) as well as isomorphic geometric motifs (cross, chevrons, nets, *etc.*) on the rock paintings from Latmos, in particular on the pregnant belly of parturient figures (Peschlow-Bindokat 2005: 53, 60-1; Peschlow-Bindokat and Gerber 2012: 93, Fig. 22). Figurines from Uğurlu (Gökçe island) are also characteristic by “exaggerated buttocks and arms making a motion toward the front of the body, curving symmetrically” (Çevik and Erdoğan 2019: 12).

74) The Marmara area, notably at Aktopraklık (Karul 2007: 386-7, Figs. 5-6) or Ilıpınar, is also rich with these isomorphic motifs (Roodenberg and Alpaslan Roodenberg 2007: 403, Fig. 19), which are probably all related to the concept of fertile exogamy.

75) Finally, undated geometric signs from Tirşin Yaylası (Özdoğan M. 2007a: 439, Figs. 7-8), found alongside the goat representations mentioned above (53), can also be interpreted as isomorphic, notably two spirals (exogamic fertility) spurring out of a unique stem (society) and two squares (moieties?) connected by a central line (society in time?).

All these geometric representations fully demonstrate these communities' high capacities of abstraction, reinforcing the idea that symbolic depictions ought never to be read for what is bluntly depicted but metaphorically for what is meant at a conceptual level.

Concluding remarks

The analysis of more than 40 Neolithic symbolic compositions has shown that, far from random, a predefined relation systematically binds elements together to build a coherent message in tune with the ideology identified in comparable ethnographic cases. The dualist scheme, based on the exogamic rule, playing a central role in the ideologies of pre-state societies, has been invoked in order to shed some light on the meaning behind the isomorphic pattern omnipresent in the Neolithic symbolism. This connection between isomorphic symbols and exogamic rule subsequently enabled to apply the same fundamental sense to more than 30 single depictions of the Neolithic Symbolic Language, be they figurative or

geometric. These numbers could grow significantly if an exhaustive approach were to be taken, maybe encompassing a wide array of prehistoric symbolic productions.

Even though details shall remain obscure, the relatively systematic match between symbolic and ideological systems seems to leave little doubt concerning the proposed connection and its general reading. The main elements (animals, humans, geometric signs, *etc.*) of the Neolithic symbolic system over time and space could thus be described as ‘ideograms’ standing for specific concepts, while their planned disposition conveys a clear message, as in a ‘script’.

Directly depicted or suggested, this standard message states that the exogamic principle renders the society's endless cycle of life and death (regeneration) possible. From there, characteristic features could be suspected, such as the systematic presence of both horns in buchrana represented in profile (the society as a strong *exogamic* entity), the difference between physical and spiritual deaths or a probable belief in some form of reincarnation. But beyond such conceptions, it was first necessary, following Gimbutas, to show that all these symbols transcribed a “language”.

Some readers may feel they are lost in this plethora of new interpretations. It is but natural since who can pretend to master a foreign language after the first lesson? As in any language, there are exceptions blurring the general pattern (‘the regenerative principle’ under a male appearance for example), but even these seem to follow an overall logic (i.e., ‘interchangeable symbols’). The greater coherence of the Neolithic symbolic system offered here, coming down to the exogamic rule, is the reason why this preliminary work ought to be followed by deeper investigations, which will certainly add symbols, refine the degree of their interpretation, and may eventually alter the rules proposed here. Future research is also expected to trace the roots of this dualistic ideology in Palaeolithic symbolism, developing what Leroi-Gourhan (1964) started to propose for the Upper Palaeolithic Franco-Cantabrian cave paintings (Lascaux, Altamira, *etc.*).

The outstanding occurrence of the exogamic concept, especially during the Neolithic period, is perfectly explainable. For the first time in human history, the old (hunter-gatherer) form of exogamy, ongoing within the larger – endogamous – tribe, was frontally challenged. The advent of the farming mode of production, which technically requires the dispersal of communities over wide landscapes and, thus, the adoption of new (termed ‘complex’) marital practices open to unrelated foreigners, was arguably the cause of this vast ideological turmoil visible in the monu-

mentality and systematisation of isomorphic representations (see Bodet 2022, 2023 for developments on this point).

If the marital pattern appears as a source of inspiration, it would be misleading to think it exhausts these communities' ideological and symbolical worlds. Exogamy must be understood as a framework and a general pattern according to which the symbolism is conceived and produced, with every community expressing it differently (these contingent differences being definable as 'cultural traits'). It is highly plausible, for example, that the symbolic language relates the deeds of mythical characters that appear in the rich cosmogonies of all traditional societies (Le Quellec 2015), like the heroes of the Dream Time for Australian Aborigines. However, a structural approach to early mythologies, as Testart (1978, 1985) endeavoured to do, shows how they are always conceived upon the same isomorphic structural conception, dualism being nothing, in basic Marxist terms, but the translation and reflection in the ideological sphere of the type of *social relations* ongoing in the realms of production and re-production.

As Max Weber (1989) showed, the ideology ought not to be conceived as a mere receptacle but as an active structure in the organisation of society. The Neolithic society, like any other society, is a complex intermingling of institutions reflecting on individuals under the form of the habitus (Barrett 2001). This surely does not mean that institutions never change. The aftermath of the Neolithic, with the advent of 'open marriages' (Lévi-Strauss' 'complex' type of kinship structure), dramatically shows it here. This internal restructuring of the society invariably reflects, in turn, on its symbolic language. For example, while we hinted at the fact that the message delivered in Göbekli Tepe was more centred on the reciprocal moieties, the same message seems to have evolved slightly in time, following changes in the social context, until it arguably became more centred around the lineage (Forest 1993, 1996b), with the advent of 'segmentary societies', as Hodder (2020: 49–51) proposed for Çatalhöyük.

In the same sociological perspective, it must finally be said that only the patient reconstruction of these Neolithic social structures and their interactions (Bodet 2009, 2012, 2019a, 2019b, 2021, 2022, 2023) could allow us to slowly follow Forest (1993, 1994, 2003, 2006, 2009) in the decipherment of this language. All these components are tightly bound to each other and make a comprehensive sense when conceived together as a complex system, which any society undoubtedly is. If symbolism is to be seen as "a product of cognitive fluidity" (Mithen 1996: 246), it is as an integrated and functional part of this greater social whole that the Symbolic Language ought to be conceived.

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Cédric Bodet

Archaeology Department
Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University
cedric.bodet@yahoo.com

Endnotes

¹ At least until the advent of complex-type societies, generally after the emergence of agriculture, for practical reasons: so that every family can settle on a separate piece of land.

² Many cultures lack a word for an ancestor, calling them spirits, shades totems ...” (Clark and Rikando 2023: 71). This quote shows how mythical figures are often confounded and find their probable origin in long-deceased ancestors.

³ “The stinger of the scorpion is a phallic symbol, and the two scissors may be birth-giving symbols.” (Van Bakel, p.10 - undated submission):

https://academia.edu/9410539/Scorpions_symbolize_fertility_on_Near_East_cylinder_seals_as_well_as_on_an_Indus_stamp

⁴ ‘Cross-cousins’ are children of a brother and a sister. They are opposed to ‘parallel cousins’ who are the children of two brothers or two sisters. Whether the community is patri- or matrilineal, cross cousins, contrary to parallel ones, automatically belong to opposite moieties and can marry each other (Ghasarian 1996).

⁵ Hollow inside (Mellaart 1967, Figs. 9 or 10) and randomly placed, even sometimes in angles, these columns are deprived of architectural function (Forest 1993: 7).

⁶ We recall that the house, as a volume, was probably considered as the womb of the lineage (Forest 1993: 14-5).

⁷ The same pictures can also be found in Hauptmann 1999: 52, Fig. 27; 2007: 130, Figs. 23-24 and Schmidt 2007b: 112, Fig. 19.

⁸ https://www.catalhoyuk.com/archive_reports/2005/ar05_29.html

⁹ For a picture, see <https://www.worldhistory.org/image/8521/two-headed-statue-from-ain-ghazal/>

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